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User-centric and data-driven retrofitting solutions for a resilient, energy-efficient, low-emission and inclusive cultural heritage.

D2.3 Study of the traditional methods and strategies used in heritage retrofitting report

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Summary

D2.3 provides an overview of different strategies suitable for EE (energy efficiency) retrofitting of heritage and historic buildings. The main criteria for the study were the acceptability of different methods and materials for use in heritage retrofitting in line with legal requirements and guidelines for heritage conservation, their cost effectiveness and availability on the market, as well as their propriety in the specific market conditions. The study concluded that one of the most important barriers to decide on the applicability of different EE retrofitting strategies, is related to heritage conservation rules and laws. The use of reversible and impermanent solutions is encouraged. In this context, the study presents a set of strategies and methods applicable under those specific conditions, focusing on the insulation of the building partitions, which still remains as the most widely used strategy for EE retrofitting of historic and heritage buildings. The report presents comparable solutions and materials which could be considered as an alternative for use in building typologies present in the project, and for use in heritage and historical buildings in general.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

BIM	Building Information Modelling
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast
EE	Energy efficiency
EP	Primary energy consumption
ERA5	Climate reanalysis by ECMWF based on the hourly data on atmospheric variables
GA	Grant agreement
EPS	Expanded polystyrene
HVAC	Heat, ventilation and air conditioning systems
NILM	Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring
NZEB	Nearly-zero Emission Buildings
PCM	Phase change materials
PIR	Polyisocyanurate
PUR	Polyurethane
PV	Photovoltaics
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SOTA	State of the art
VOC	Volatile organic compounds
XPS	Extruded polystyrene
ZEB	Zero Emission Buildings

Executive summary

This report provides an overview of different strategies (methods and materials), suitable for EE retrofitting of heritage and historic buildings. EE retrofitting processes, in general, encompass a wide range of possible interventions, which include: insulation of building partitions, installation of energy-efficient lighting, replacement of old HVAC systems, water-saving measures, installation of PV systems, addition of smart thermostats and other connected devices, better air filtration and ventilation, efficient appliances. Some of those solutions might have a high impact on the parameters and visual context of a building, as well as they might perform differently in different climate conditions. Therefore, they must be analysed for their suitability in use in heritage and historic buildings.

The main criteria for the study were the acceptability of different methods and materials for use in heritage retrofitting in line with the legal requirements and guidelines for heritage conservation, their cost effectiveness and availability on the market, as well as their propriety in the specific market conditions. Therefore, the report starts with the overview of the climate conditions in zones, which are represented in the project by the demo sites, the legal limitations of certain interventions in heritage and historic buildings, as well as of the technical barriers to the use of some materials and methods commonly applied in non-historic sites. Further, the report presents solutions, which can be utilized in the context of historic buildings.

According to the Köppen-Geiger classification, the demo sites are located in four climate zones – Dfb (Tartu, Estonia), Cfa (Bologna, Italy), Cfb (Aguilar de Campoo, Spain), Csa (Funchal, Madeira) – which have visibly different characteristics, especially in terms of yearly average temperature and sunshine duration. The colder climate of Dfb class might necessitate the use of materials with better insulation performance (λ 0,030-0,045W/mK). The lower insolation, especially during winter, severely limits the performance of PV systems and decreases the ability for passive heating of the building. On the other hand, the warmer climate of Southern Europe needs a careful consideration of EE strategies performance during the summer, as the lack of proper natural ventilation combined with high performance of building insulation might cause an entrapment of heat inside the building, causing an overreliance on continuous cooling systems. In all cases, there is a visible variability of temperature over the year, which might be a cause for consideration when utilizing different internal insulation methods.

The study concluded that one of the most important barriers to decide on the applicability of different EE retrofitting strategies, is related to heritage conservation rules and laws. While there are some differences in terms of the conservation systems' organisation of both analysed cases (Italy and Poland), it is forbidden to carry out any type of intervention with a significant impact on the visual characteristics of the building, or that could interfere with traditional construction methods. These stem from specific laws or from additional conservation guidelines. Therefore, the use of strategies involving external insulation solutions, installation of façade solar panels and, in some cases, replacement of windows, is not possible. Any other strategy which might include permanent changes in the state of the building require careful consideration

and consultation with the conservation authority. The use of reversible and impermanent solutions is encouraged.

In this context, the study presents a set of strategies and methods that are applicable under those specific conditions, focusing in particular on the insulation of the building partitions, which still remain the most widely used strategy for EE retrofitting of historic and heritage buildings. The report presents comparable solutions and materials which could be considered as an alternative for use in the typologies of buildings represented in the project, and for use in heritage and historical buildings in general.

Planned criteria

The objective of this task is to map current solutions accessible in the market and identify main advantages and barriers in their implementation in order to establish a comparative with solutions proposed in Herit4ages and set the targets to achieve in the KPIs (Task 2.5.). Given the specific conditions and technical requirements of heritage energy retrofitting, the aspects of climatic conditions of the retrofitted site, as well as the acceptability of the strategies from the preservation of heritage standpoint given the generalized legal limitations and technical requirements of interventions in heritage buildings, are used as the primary criteria for analysis of heritage energy retrofitting strategies. The aspects such as cost-effectiveness, energy performance, types of installation, disruptiveness, built environment's life cycle, operational costs, preservation of heritage, compatibility with traditional materials, sustainability, social acceptance, etc., were used to describe different retrofitting strategies when relevant. The typologies described in task 2.2 will be used as examples to compare the different solutions.

1. Introduction

The main objective of Herit4Ages is to develop and validate a set of technical and socially innovative sustainable energy and resource-efficient solutions for the cost-effective improvement and preservation of our cultural built environment heritage along relevant aspects such as: inclusiveness, accessibility, resilience, environmental and energy performance. One of the important aspects for the future development of the Herit4Ages solutions is the future replicability of these solutions beyond the demo site countries. The aim of the study performed by LWIT and UNIBO, which is summarised in this report, was to provide an insight for T2.5 (setting out the KPIs) by setting out the reference point for the comparison of Herit4Ages solutions to the materials and techniques, that are available on the market.

During the course of the study, when setting the criteria to choose these comparable solutions, a comparative analysis of the legal and technical barriers in Italy and in Poland was established, to showcase the details of how the heritage conservation and protection systems work in different countries with contrasting climates. This two-country focus also highlights the differences in the technical and standardisation framework that will lead to the adoption of certain construction processes, methods and materials used in energy retrofitting of heritage buildings, even if the range of applicable materials and techniques are effectively the same.

It was seen that, from the perspective of the conservation laws and guidelines existing in those two countries, the same range of technologies and techniques is either barred from use in heritage projects, or at least severely limited, and for the same reasons. For example, in both cases preservation of the original façade as the main objective, limits the use of external insulation techniques and methods, regardless of the exact legal base or procedure which allows the conservation officer to decide on this matter.

Hence, the general outline of legal aspects regulating the EE retrofitting process for heritage buildings is extremely important, since conservation officers can approve or disapprove the use of certain types of materials or methods for the specific site.

Deliverable D2.3 *Study of the traditional methods and strategies used in heritage retrofitting report* was created in the frame of T2.3 *Study of the traditional methods and strategies used in heritage retrofitting*. The main aim of this study was to map the existing state of the art solutions available on the market in order to establish a comparison between Herit4Ages solutions and market-ready retrofitting solutions traditionally used in the energy retrofitting of heritage buildings. In this context, the study focused on describing and providing data on the market-available solutions and strategies, together with their approximate technical parameters, installation methods and adaptability to different typologies of heritage buildings.

This study sets out several specific objectives to help reach its main goal by providing a broader context from the standpoint of technical and market validity of different retrofitting solutions:

- Objective 1: to describe the influence of climatic conditions of the demo sites on the market requirements regarding the materials and strategies used on those markets.

- Objective 2: to define the barriers which might constrain the use of certain retrofitting strategies and methods in the context of heritage buildings.
- Objective 3: to present the retrofitting strategies which are applicable within the constraints of those climatic, legal and technical barriers.

To realize those objectives, the following report is built around two distinct sections. Section 2 describes the general constraints and considerations, which limit the set of applicable energy retrofitting solutions in heritage buildings. This chapter describes the characteristics of climate zones in which the demo sites are located, as well as the different heritage conservation laws and technical limitations which might influence the adaptability of the energy retrofitting solutions available on the market for use in the heritage buildings. In that regard, the study does provide the general climatic, legal and technical context of different renovation strategies, referring to the demo site context and other supporting areas (mostly Poland), in order to describe the reasoning behind the acceptance of certain solutions and the lack thereof in case of other solutions. However, it is not a detailed study of those aspects, which are under the scope of other tasks (T2.1, T2.2, T2.4), but rather builds upon that knowledge focusing purely on the applicability of described retrofitting solutions.

Section 3 describes traditional retrofitting solutions which are comparable to the solutions proposed by Herit4ages. This study of the retrofitting strategies describes in general the available paths of EE retrofitting of heritage buildings, but gives particular attention to the aspect of building insulation, which constitutes the most widely used 'traditional' retrofitting method that is comparable to Herit4ages solutions.

This report sets the framework of reference for the task 2.5 *Definition of key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate solution performance and acceptance*. The deliverable provides the description and the data on the solutions comparable to the solutions proposed in Herit4ages in the context of traditional retrofitting strategies.

Energy efficiency retrofitting concept in context of Herit4ages solutions

EE retrofit is a process of improvement of the energy performance in the existing building stock, leading to the lowering of the environmental footprint of the building during its lifetime. EE retrofitting measures include a wide range of solutions, which include the improvement of the building envelope performance and energy efficient solutions on the level of energy consumption: energy efficient lighting and appliances, energy and building management systems, RES integration (in particular PV), HVAC optimization [1].

It is important to note, that some of those solutions do have a significant impact on the visual and technical characteristics of the building. External insulation methods irreversibly alter the look of the façade by covering its original features. In many cases, replacement of doors and windows would have a similar effect on the visual perception of the building, and likewise the installation of PV systems, especially in the visible areas of the facades, even though there are possibilities to make them less visible. The implementation of certain energy efficient appliances, and energy and building management systems might involve changes in the electrical setup or other vital systems of the building. While in the context of new and non-historic buildings these are purely aesthetic and technical considerations, it is effectively a deciding factor as to whether the specific approach can be utilized in the case of heritage and historical buildings.

In this context, Herit4ages presents a set of technical and societal solutions, which aim at propagating the idea of EE retrofitting in the context of heritage buildings. The technical solutions of the project include:

- Green environmental sensor,
- Energy router and NILM,
- Integrated BIM-based Herit4Ages Digital Twin Ecosystem,
- Internal insulation system for reversible installation, based on the sustainable insulation boards.

Herit4ages demo sites

1. Aguilar de Campoo, Spain – Romanesque hermitage of Canduela
 - Construction year: Constructed: 13th Century/ Renovated: 1990 and 2012;
 - Building use: Experimental Centre / Laboratory;
 - Net floor area: 52 m²;
 - Construction features: Single volume building with 208 m³. Flooring and original sandstone walls. Thickness of the walls between 1 and 1.5 m. Wooden door with non-watertight closure, automatic opening by means of a magnetic card. Gabled roof with oak wood structure, built in 1990, without insulation, topped with ceramic tile.

2. Aguilar de Campoo, Spain – Posada Santa María la Real
 - Construction and renovation year: constructed - end of 18th Century; renovated – 1995;
 - Building use: accommodation (hotel);
 - Net floor area: 1456 m²;
 - Construction features: Two-storey building with a wooden structure and a gabled roof topped with corbels, ground floor with masonry walls and window openings with wooden lintel embedded in the wall, first floor with brick façade finish and lintelled windows with traditional carpentry and stained-glass windows. In 1995, the building was renovated to make it suitable for tourist accommodation.
3. Bologna, Italy – Historical building of engineering at the University of Bologna
 - Construction year: constructed – 1932-1935; renovated – no unitary project, several interventions;
 - Building use: university classes and offices;
 - Net floor area: 18.860 m² (on four storeys);
 - Construction features: Mixed masonry-concrete structure and different types of windows (aluminium and double glazing, wood and single or double glazing, iron and single glazing). Minor renovations were carried out since the building construction to make it adequate for regulatory needs (safety, HVAC, windows).
4. Funchal, Portugal – Santa Maria, 25
 - Construction year: constructed – 1937; renovated – 2006;
 - Building use: housing building;
 - Net floor area: 56.5 m² per floor;
 - Construction features: Stone masonry exterior walls and concrete block masonry.
5. Tartu, Estonia – Korporatsioon Vironia
 - Construction year: constructed – 1778; renovated – 1996-2022;
 - Building use: office building;
 - Net floor area: 2273 m²;
 - Construction features: application construction – bricks, Finishing – plaster, Siding – concrete and wood, Roof – metal roof (tin).

2. Technical, legal and climatic context of energy retrofitting of heritage buildings

2.1. Climatic conditions of the demo sites

One of the aspects to be considered when selecting the appropriate energy retrofitting strategy are the climatic conditions of the given site, as they define the specific measures to be taken. Therefore, the relevant strategies related to Herit4ages solutions must be evaluated considering the specific conditions of the 5 demo sites in 4 locations involved in the project: Tartu (Estonia), Bologna (Italy), Aguilar de Campoo (Spain), Funchal (Madeira, Portugal).

The Köppen-Geiger classification defines over 10 distinct climate classes present in Europe [2], which represent a diverse range and types of impact on the built environment. The specific cases of Herit4ages demo sites are located in the opposite ends of the temperature variation scale, with Italian, Spanish and Madeiran demo sites representing either hot or warm temperate climate classes, and Estonian demo site located in a cold climate class, representative to much of Central and Eastern Europe.

FIGURE 1 KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLASSIFICATION OF CLIMATE ZONES IN EUROPE (WITHOUT MADEIRA). SOURCE: H. BECK ET AL. [3]

Given the abovementioned characteristics of the demo sites, the following sections, as well as the further study of the retrofitting strategies and their legal or technical constraints, present the subject separately for the colder, Baltic zone, and for the warmer Mediterranean zone. The first part refers to the specific data regarding the city of Tartu and Estonia in general, and additionally to the supporting example of Poland. The second part focuses entirely on the climatic zones which characterize the three remaining demo sites, representative to a large part of Mediterranean region.

2.1.1. A brief description of the climatic conditions of countries located in the Baltic zone

Most of the region, including Estonia, is located within the warm summer humid continental climate (Dfb), which encompasses most of Central and Eastern Europe, and a considerable part of Northern Europe. In this context, one of the most important factors shaping the climate of different parts of the Baltic region is its geographical location. Estonia is located between 57°30'N and 59°50'N, which are closer to the subarctic regions. This makes the location in Tartu visibly colder compared to Poland, which is located between 49°00'N and 54°50'N, i.e. in medium latitudes typical for a Dfb climate in Europe.

The significant impacts on the climate resulting from such a location include:

- The maximum solar altitude angle for Tartu, Estonia, is ranging from maximum 55°06' to minimum of 8°18', compared to the maximum of 58°36' to 64°26' in Poland, with a minimum from 11°44' to 17°34'.
- Differentiation of the amount of maximum solar energy reaching southern and northern areas of the Dfb zone, which statistically causes a differentiation of air temperature on that axis [4, p. 5].
- Higher insolation of southern terrain exposures and buildings located on them, typical for the location in the northern hemisphere.

Another very important factor influencing the climate of the entire climate of Northern Europe is the warm North Atlantic Current (Gulf Stream). It contributes to the increase in temperature throughout Europe and the general moderation of its climate. In this context, the distance of different parts of the region from the ocean is also important. The Atlantic, affecting Western Europe, causes the western part of the Baltic zone is influenced the most, leading to a more oceanic climate and resulting in smaller temperature amplitudes, increasing the amount of precipitation and the average air temperature [4, p. 6]. The areas located further east or north-east, including Baltic States, located closer to Central Asia, have greater influences of the continental climate. Such a location of Poland - between the Atlantic in the west and the vast continent in the east, affects the transitional nature of the climate of Poland.

Another important factor is the terrain of Poland. The lack of natural barriers on the east-west axis and minimal barriers from the north, with the simultaneous predominance of lowlands, allows the free flow of masses both from the west and from the east, as shown by the data regarding atmospheric circulation in Poland [4, pp. 35-38]. Such terrain is also characteristic for areas to the north and east from Poland, i.e. for the Baltic States and Belarus, which is well illustrated by the physical map of Europe below. The climate of the Southern Baltic region is also influenced by the large forest cover, especially in the Baltic States, extending further east to Belarus and Russia. As a result, Estonian climate is shaped by predominantly western, south-western and southern winds [5].

FIGURE 2 PHYSICAL MAP OF EUROPE. SOURCE: EEA [6].

Essential features of the Dfb climate

The geographical features of the area lead to the following characteristics of the climate in Tartu demo site [7]:

- The average air temperature for the period of 1991-2020 is 6.3°C.
- Avg. precipitation for the period of 1991-2020 is 673 mm per year, with the relative humidity of 79%.
- Avg. sunshine duration in the period of 1991-2020 was 1736 hours.
- Avg. air pressure at sea level for the period of 1991-2020 was around 1005.1 hPa, but with high variability throughout the year.

For comparison, this climate zone further to the south, on the example of Poland, has the following characteristics [8]:

- The average annual temperature for the period 1991-2020 was 8.7°C.
- Average precipitation in Poland is currently about 600 mm per year with the highest level in the summer months and shows an upward trend to the level of 650 mm.
- In the Transitional Temperate Climate, cloudiness prevails. In Poland, the sun shines for about 47% of the time, on average from about 1400 - 1900 hours per year, with an average for central Poland at the level of 1600 hours.

- Normal air pressure in Poland is 1013 hPa, but it is characterized by high variability throughout the year.
- Clearly distinctive seasons (conventionally - 4, thermally - 6 to -8).
- Relative stability with a small number of extreme weather phenomena (increasing, however, due to climate change).

The Transitional Temperate Climate, like other climate zones, is subject to changes. The last 30 years were on average 1,2°C warmer than the previous period. The years 2018-2020 were the warmest in the history of Poland, with the winter of 2019/2020 was the warmest winter in the history of measurements in Poland, and the summer of 2019 - the warmest in the history of measurements. Precipitation is also increasing (summarily), but their spatial and temporal variability is significantly increasing. Heavy rains and violent storms are observed more often, which means that precipitation norms in many places are significantly exceeded, while at the same time there are multi-week droughts in other places [4].

Air masses shaping weather conditions in the Transitional Temperate Climate Zone

In addition to the climate, in the area of Southern Baltic countries, weather conditions are characterized by high variability and instability, due to the frequent changes in air flow directions. This is the result of the action of two main factors shaping weather conditions, which are [9, p. 32]:

- Atmospheric pressure systems over Europe and Asia - Northeastern Europe (including Baltic Sea region) is most often either under the influence of North Atlantic Oscillation, with heavy influence of Icelandic Low (mainly in winter) or the Azores High (in the summer period), less often under the influence of the Asian High.
- Inflow of air masses over Northeastern Europe - The inflow of air from other parts of the world, mainly outside Europe, shapes weather conditions in this region.

This pattern of circulation seems consistent throughout the Baltic Sea region, considering the data available for other Baltic countries, including Latvia [10] and Estonia [11].

The most important is the polar-maritime air, which accounts for over 60% of the total inflow of air masses in Poland [9, p. 33]. It forms over the Atlantic and moves from the west to Europe. This mass is characterized by high humidity. Its characteristic features are :

- Appearance in all seasons.
- Decrease in temperature and increase in cloudiness and frontal precipitation in the summer period.
- Increase in temperature (usually thaw or frost relief) and precipitation of rain or snow in the winter period along with possible fogs.

Another important mass is the polar-continental air flowing from the east. It accounts for over 30% of the air masses lying over Northeastern Europe [9, p. 33]. It is formed in Central Asia, and is characterised by low humidity. Its characteristic features are:

- Appearance in all seasons.
- Occurrence of heat and clear, sunny weather in the summer period with the possibility of violent storms.
- Occurrence of severe frosts in winter with clear sunny weather.

Polar-maritime air and polar-continental air play a key role, due to their free flow of air on the latitudinal axis.

The remaining air masses in this region of Europe account for less than 10% of the total air movement. Their inflow is limited by distances and the barrier of mountain ranges (north - Scandinavian mountains, south - Carpathians and other European ranges). The most important of them are [9, p. 33]:

- Arctic air, appearing over the region mainly in winter, but also in spring and autumn. This air flows from over the Arctic Ocean or northern Scandinavia, and accounts for about 4% of air masses. In winter, it brings frost, usually with sunny weather, and in spring and autumn, it causes frosts.
- Tropical maritime air, flowing from the southwest, comes from the Azores archipelago. It accounts for only 1-2% of air masses over the region. It appears both in summer and in winter. In summer, it brings heat with storms, in winter - intense thaws threatening floods and flooding.

Tropical continental air, appearing from the southeast direction, coming from over Asia Minor or North Africa, also accounts for no more than 1-2% of air masses over the region. It can appear in the summer period, and cause heat and drought. In spring, it is responsible for an unusual influx of heat for this period, in autumn it brings sunny and rainless weather [9, p. 33].

2.1.2. A brief description of the climatic conditions of countries located in the Mediterranean zone

The demo sites belonging to the South European region are located in Bologna (Italy), Aguilar de Campóo (Spain), and Funchal (Portugal). They belong to different climatic regions, respectively "Humid Subtropical", "Temperate Oceanic" and "Hot-Summer Mediterranean", corresponding to "Cfa", "Cfb" and "Csa" classes of the Köppen-Geiger classification [12]. These categories represent diverse climatic conditions that significantly represent the whole South European territory.

Given the particular conformation of the countries hosting the demo sites, which are all characterized by very different climatic areas according to the Köppen-Geiger classification, the discussion will start with a brief overview of the climatic conditions of these geographic areas. Then, it will provide more details about the local contexts where the demo sites are situated to better study the working climatic conditions that directly affect the research project.

The **Italian peninsula**, between 36°50'N and 47°00'N, is characterized by a distinctive geographical layout that includes the Mediterranean Sea, plains, hills, and mountains. This diverse geography results in a variety of climatic zones across the country. In the southern regions and along the western coast, the climate is predominantly classified as "Csa", known as the "Hot Summer Mediterranean Climate." Moving towards the central coast near the Apennines and the north-central inland areas, the climate transitions to Cfa, or "Humid Subtropical Climate." These climatic conditions also represent **France's southern coast**, which is characterized by a Mediterranean climate, and the entire **Balkan Peninsula**, with the southern part near Greece and the Adriatic coasts featuring a Mediterranean climate and the inland areas being more temperate. The foothills of the Alps in the North are instead classified as "Cfb", or "Oceanic Climate," and further up into

the Alps, the climate becomes "Dfb", characterized as "Humid Continental with Mild Summers," and Dfc, which is a "Subarctic Climate with Cool Summers" [12].

Italy can be divided into six climatic zones depending on the average temperatures and the degree-days [13], which can be further grouped within three main geographical zones:

- North: Northern Italy, which includes the Alpine regions and the Po Valley, has a continental climate. Winters can be cold and foggy, especially in inland areas, with temperatures that can drop below zero. Summer is hot and humid. Precipitation is abundant, especially in the Alpine and pre-Alpine regions, and can be snowy in winter.
- Center: The climate of the central area, which includes cities like Rome and Florence, is transitional. It has characteristics of both continental and Mediterranean climates, with mild and humid winters and hot, dry summers. Precipitation is mainly concentrated in the autumn and spring months.
- South and islands: Southern Italy, Sicily, and Sardinia enjoy a Mediterranean climate, with mild winters and hot, dry summers. Winter mean temperatures rarely drop below 10°C, while in summer, they can easily exceed 30°C, especially in the inland and southern areas.

The Italian coasts, particularly those facing the Tyrrhenian and Adriatic Seas, typically enjoy milder winters and summers tempered by the sea breeze. In contrast, the inland and mountainous regions may experience more extreme climatic conditions, with cold winters and hot summers. The Alps and the Apennines significantly influence the climate, serving as barriers to winds and leading to considerable local variations [14].

The **Iberian Peninsula**, including Spain and Portugal, is located between 36°00'N and 44°00'N. It is geographically shaped mainly by the Mediterranean Sea to the East and the Atlantic Ocean to the West. Compared to the Italian one, the Iberian Peninsula extends more longitudinally. These unique conditions reflect a variety of climatic zones, some of which differ from those in Italy. There is a significant variation between the southern and northern areas. The southern regions feature a "Cold Semi-Arid" (BSk) climate in the interior and along the Mediterranean, a "Cold Desert" (BWk) climate in the southwestern tip near the Mediterranean, and a "Hot-Summer Mediterranean" (Csa) climate on the western coasts and in the interior areas closer to the Atlantic Ocean. In the northern regions, there are more oceanic influences, with the northern coast and interior featuring a "Temperate Oceanic" (Cfb) climate, while the coasts of northern Portugal and Galicia experience a "Warm-Summer Mediterranean" (Csb) climate. The mountainous areas around the Pyrenees exhibit even more diverse climatic conditions, up to Dfc, which is "Subarctic With Cool Summers And Year-Round Rainfall" [12].

The peninsula's diverse landscape gives rise to a variety of climatic conditions across the territory, broadly categorized into many geographical and climate zones influenced by topography and altitude [15], [16]. In the highest regions, a variety of microclimates are present, encompassing dry continental, alpine, and even subarctic climates at the summit of mountain ranges such as the Sierra Nevada, Cantabrian Mountains, and

the Pyrenees. Excluding Spain's northernmost part, the country generally features a dry, sunny, and warm climate on average. Some regions also encounter a hot desert climate, particularly along parts of the southeastern coast. These geographical distinctions underscore the vast diversity of Spain's climates, shaped by its intricate topography, which includes mountain ranges, plateaus, and extensive coastlines.

In summary, for Spain:

- Atlantic coasts are characterized by a cool climate typical of Atlantic shores, marked by humidity and rainfall.
- The central plateaus experience a continental and arid climate, as seen in areas like Madrid, with cold winters and often scorching summers.
- The South and the East of Spain enjoy a Mediterranean climate.
- Mountainous areas in the Pyrenees and Sierra can be very cold, with temperatures getting colder with the altitude.
- In Andalusia, the climate is similar to that of northern Africa, due to its warm, dry conditions, especially during the summer months, with high temperatures and low rainfall.

Portugal also experiences different region's weather patterns [17], [18]:

- Northern Portugal features a maritime temperate climate with abundant rainfall throughout the year, particularly in winter, and warm summers. Cooler temperatures are experienced in the inland areas, and snow in mountain areas is possible.
- Central Portugal serves as a transition zone, with coastal areas like Coimbra and Lisbon experiencing mild winters and warm, dry summers, while inland and higher elevations see colder winters and hot summers.
- Southern Portugal has a hot-summer Mediterranean climate, with hot/warm summers and mild winters.
- Madeira and the Azores archipelagos have instead oceanic climates. Madeira has mild temperatures and moderate rainfall year-round, while the Azores feature a humid, temperate maritime climate with consistent temperatures and higher precipitation.

Essential features of the Humid Subtropical Climate (in the example of Bologna, Italy)

The city of Bologna is located in the north-central part of the Italian peninsula, around 44°50' N, within the "Cfa" zone, corresponding to "Humid Subtropical Climate". This zone encompasses a significant portion of the Italian territory, including some central regions near the Adriatic Sea and much of Northern Italy, just below the Alps. Geographically, this area includes the Po Valley, situated between the Alps and the Apennines, which are the first and second highest mountain ranges in the country, respectively.

The significant elements of the climate resulting from such a location include [19]:

- The maximum solar altitude angle is about 69°, and the minimum is 22°.
- Winters are cold and humid, with temperatures often hovering around zero. Snow is not frequent.
- Summers in Bologna are hot and humid, with temperatures that can easily exceed 30°C during the hottest days. The high humidity can make the heat more oppressive. Evenings can be cooler, but the humidity remains high.
- Precipitation is evenly distributed throughout the year, with peaks in spring and autumn.
- In autumn and winter, Bologna can be subject to fog, especially in the morning and nighttime hours, influenced by the proximity of the Reno River and the region's plain topography.
- These transition seasons are generally mild and pleasant, with temperatures gradually increasing in spring and decreasing in autumn.

Bologna's location in the extensive Po Valley (Pianura Padana) and its relative distance from the sea mean that the city does not fully benefit from the sea breezes that moderate temperatures in the coastal areas of Emilia-Romagna. This results in hotter summers and colder winters compared to the region's coastal areas.

Additional significant climate data [20], [21] includes:

- Average annual temperature equal to was 14.8°C (for the period 2000-2020).
- Average precipitation is about 850 mm per year, with the highest levels occurring in the spring and autumn.
- Western winds predominate in winter, while the South wind dominates in summer, with an average speed of 3 m/s and a maximum of 11 m/s.
- Overcast days are prevalent in this climate, but there are many clear days, especially in summer. In Bologna, the sun shines about 65% of the time, averaging around 2000 hours per year.
- The mean normal pressure is 1016 hPa, but it is characterized by high variability throughout the year.
- There is relative stability with a few extreme weather phenomena, which, however, are increasing due to climate change.

The Humid Subtropical Climate is not immune to changes. In 2018, average temperatures in Emilia-Romagna were 1.66°C higher than those recorded between 1971 and 2000. Moreover, they have progressively risen since then. The year 2023 was the hottest ever recorded in Bologna. Particularly notable was the autumn of 2023, which became the warmest autumn ever measured in the city, with average maximum temperatures exceeding those of the 1991-2020 period by 3.1°C. Increasingly frequent are the occurrences of heavy rainfall and intense storms, leading to precipitation levels that far surpass the norm in several regions (how happened in the catastrophic events of spring 2023), while concurrently, other areas experience prolonged droughts [19].

Essential features of the Temperate Oceanic Climate (in the example of Aguilar de Campóo, Spain)

Aguilar de Campóo is situated in the north-central part of the Iberian Peninsula, located in the province of Palencia in the Castile and León region of Spain, roughly around the coordinates 42°50'N latitude. This location places it within a transitional climate zone, blending characteristics of the oceanic climate from the North with the continental and Mediterranean influences of the interior Meseta Central of Spain. This positioning results in a climate with distinct seasonal variations [22].

The significant elements of the climate resulting from such a location include:

- The maximum solar altitude angle is about 71°, and the minimum is 24°.
- The summers are short, comfortable, dry, and mostly clear.
- The winters are long, very cold, snowy, windy, and partly cloudy, with temperatures that can drop below freezing.
- Precipitation occurs throughout the year but is more abundant in autumn and winter.

The proximity to the Cantabrian Mountains can influence weather conditions, resulting in variations in local climate. Snowfall is common in the winter, with about eight days of snow per year, especially in the nearby elevated areas of Palencia.

Additional significant climate data [23] is:

- The average annual temperature is about 12°C with an average humidity of around 67%.
- The average precipitation in Palencia is currently about 493 mm per year, with rain on approximately 29% of the days.
- The prevailing winds come from the Southwest and northeast in winter, with maximum speeds of about 11 m/s. In summer, Northeast winds prevail, and these also prevail at moderate speeds, averaging around 3 to 5 m/s.
- There are about 3050 hours of sunshine annually, about 35% of the annual hours, especially in summer when the sky is clear.

Climate change has already impacted the Palencia region over the last 40 years. This is evidenced by the ERA5 data source, the fifth generation of ECMWF atmospheric global climate reanalysis, which spans from 1979 to 2021 [24]. For Palencia, there's been a notable increase in average temperatures, approximately 1.2°C from 1979 to 2021, aligning with the broader global warming patterns. This warming trend contributes to a higher risk of wildfires and freak storms, phenomena that are becoming more frequent and severe due to climate change.

Essential features of the Hot-Summer Mediterranean Climate (in the example of Funchal, Portugal)

Funchal is located on Madeira Island (Portugal) in the Atlantic Ocean, at coordinates 32°39'N 16°54'W. It is the island's largest city. Funchal's climate is primarily influenced by the ocean and its latitude, contributing to its pleasant weather [22].

Key climate characteristics include:

- A maximum solar angle of approximately 81°, and a minimum of 34°.
- Winters are very mild, summers are warm and dry, and there's little temperature variation between seasons, keeping the distinction between them subtle.
- Wind is common, with rain being rare in summer and frequent in winter.

Additional key climate data includes [25]:

- An average annual temperature of around 19°C, with the coldest month being January (min temperature around 10°C) and the warmest month being August (max temperature around 31°C).
- The dominant winds, stronger than in previously analyzed climates, blow from the North in both winter and summer.

As for other areas, climate change has affected Madeira, with anticipated scenarios for 2050 and 2070 predicting an average temperature rise of 1.4 to 3.7 °C and a decrease in precipitation by 30 to 40%, impacting agriculture and ecosystem sustainability [26].

Air masses shaping weather conditions in the Southern Belt of Europe

Weather conditions in the Mediterranean are marked by significant variability and instability due to its geographical location, the diversity of its landscape, which includes extensive coastlines, hills, mountains, and valleys, and the influence of various pressure systems and air masses. The air masses that characterize the area can be distinguished by their origin (arctic, polar, or subtropical) and their thermodynamic characteristics, classified as warm or cold depending on whether their temperature is higher or lower than that of the surface over which they are situated.

The main air masses that determine the weather conditions in the Mediterranean are: the maritime Arctic Air, Continental Arctic Air, Cold Maritime Polar Air, Cold Continental Polar Air, Warm Maritime Polar Air, Warm Continental Polar Air, Maritime Tropical Air, and Continental Tropical Air. Below is provided a brief description [27], [28].

Maritime Arctic Air, or mAk:

- The flow of this air mass into Europe is typically facilitated by a thermal anticyclone positioned over Greenland or, more often, by the dynamic force exerted by the Azores high moving toward the Arctic latitudes of the Atlantic Ocean.
- This air mass is present throughout the year, with the exceptions of July and August.
- It is characterized by its cold nature, especially at higher altitudes, and is known for its moisture and instability.

Continental Arctic Air, or cA:

- It originates from the cold air that accumulates at the surface under the influence of the Russian-Siberian thermal anticyclone.
- On rare occasions, it reaches Italian region, bringing with it significant cold spells known as "Burian" or severe snowstorms, known in some contexts as blizzards.
- This air mass is considered the coldest that can impact the Italian peninsula. Its chilling presence is most felt in Italy when the anticyclone extends a ridge towards the Balkans, simultaneously with a deepening depression over the central or west-central Mediterranean.
- This air mass comes from regions such as the Barents Sea, Novaya Zemlya, Northern Russia, and Siberia, and its influence is typically from late October to early April.

Cold Maritime Polar Air, or mPk:

- It is influenced by the dynamic anticyclone situated over the mid-Atlantic, West of the British Isles, and is associated with the cold sector of the polar front's undulation.
- It can travel great distances, even originating from across the ocean. The origins of this air mass are in the North Atlantic, including regions like Labrador, Newfoundland, and Canada.
- It is present throughout the year, characterized by a cooling effect that is more noticeable in summer during the passage of a cold front; conversely, in winter, mPk can disperse the ground-level inversion layer, leading to a slight increase in temperature.
- It is a relatively moist and generally unstable air mass, identifiable by satellite images showing numerous cumuliform clouds.

Cold Continental Polar Air, or cPk:

- It originates from the extensive thermal anticyclones that dominate Russia and Central-Eastern Europe during the winter.
- These anticyclones are long-lasting and continuously rejuvenated by the influx of Arctic air, which establishes a solid ground-level thermal inversion, a hallmark of cPk over time.
- This air mass stems from regions like Southern Russia, the Balkans, and Central-Eastern Europe, and it primarily influences the weather during the winter season.
- It is cold in the lower layers and is characterized by frequent thermal inversions. As it makes its way to Mediterranean regions, it crosses the sea, picking up moisture in the process.

Warm Maritime Polar Air, or mPw:

- It forms in the warm sector of a polar front wave, often near the northern edge of the Azores high.
- In some cases, it originates from the transformation of Cold Maritime Polar Air (mPk) that has lingered for an extended period over the mid-latitudes of the Atlantic Ocean near a high-pressure area.
- For these reasons, this air mass appears in the warm sector of an extratropical cyclone, particularly developed in winter.
- It is present mainly during the winter season. In terms of physical characteristics, it is cool in summer and mild in winter; it is very humid and not particularly unstable.

Warm Maritime Polar Air, or mPw:

- It emerges within the warm sector of a polar front undulation, frequently close to the northern boundary of the Azores high.
- Sometimes, it results from the transformation of Cold Maritime Polar Air (mPk) that has lingered over the mid-latitudes of the Atlantic Ocean near a high-pressure area for an extended period.
- Due to these factors, this air mass is particularly evident in the developed warm sector of an extratropical cyclone during winter.
- Originating from the Atlantic, specifically between 40° and 50° latitude, mPw is mainly a winter phenomenon. It's characterized by being cool in the summer and mild in the winter, with high humidity and moderate stability.

Warm Continental Polar Air, or cPw:

- It is a typical summer air mass that forms over the low-pressure barometric and transient anticyclones of Southeastern Europe due to the radiative heating of the continent or the transformation of a pre-existing post-frontal cold air mass.
- This air mass originates from areas such as Southern Russia, the Balkans, and Turkey, and it predominantly occurs during the summer.
- Its physical characteristics include warming from the ground up due to radiation; initially, it is dry but has the potential to become unstable.

Maritime Tropical Air, or mT,

- It is produced along the southwestern edge of the Azores high; it reaches the Mediterranean on a southWest flow through Gibraltar or Morocco, most often drawn by low-pressure centers that have formed between the Balearic Islands and the Gulf of Lyon following previous incursions of cold air types like mA or mPk.
- As a result, it often brings rain.
- This air mass rarely reaches Central Europe via the Bay of Biscay.
- It is present throughout the year.
- Its physical characteristics include being warm and very humid, with high specific humidity throughout the air column, and it is initially relatively stable.

Continental Tropical Air, or cT:

- It ascends from the western edge of dynamic subtropical anticyclones, originating from North Africa, Asia Minor, and Southeastern Europe.
- This air mass is associated with the dynamic pushes of subtropical high pressures, which can lead it to reach Italy with an anticyclonic action that makes it even hotter and drier through subsidence (leading to torrid summer heat).
- In the colder half of the year, it resembles mT, as it becomes particularly enriched with water vapor collected during its long journey over the Mediterranean.
- It is considered the warmest air mass that can reach Italy.
- This air mass is present throughout the year and is very hot and humid in all seasons, especially when linked to cyclonic conditions. It is potentially unstable, with thermal gradients higher than those of mT.

2.2. Technical and legal barriers for energy retrofitting of heritage buildings in Italy and Poland

This section presents the main legal and technical barriers, which are an important factor limiting the use of certain energy retrofitting strategies in some typologies of heritage buildings. This study focused on the general representation of legal and technical limitations of heritage retrofitting strategies, rather than being a detailed study of policies and laws regulating those aspects in demo site countries and the EU in general. As such, in the context of legal aspects the study has taken the representative examples of Italy and Poland.

It is important to note, that the methods for energy retrofitting of heritage buildings are not regulated at the EU-level. In terms of regulations on improving the energy efficiency of buildings, EU Member States are obliged to submit to the European Commission the national action plans containing information on planned actions in this area. Point 18 of the preamble to Directive (EU) 2018/844 of the European Parliament (Energy Performance of Buildings Directive – EPBD) and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency states, that *scientific research should be supported on new solutions to improve the energy performance of buildings and historic objects, as well as testing such solutions while ensuring the protection and preservation of cultural heritage* [29].

However, the mentioned directive is only a general framework, which means that it does not establish uniform requirements applicable in all EU countries. Member States are only obliged to establish specific requirements and introduce appropriate mechanisms in relation to the energy performance of buildings, which will apply on their territory. Likewise, the EU does not regulate the limitations as to the retrofitting strategies, i.e. types of materials, installation strategies and so on, which are defined as a part of the national heritage conservation systems.

2.2.1. Review of the regulations governing the renovation of historic buildings in the climatic conditions of Northern Europe (on the example of Poland)

Due to historic circumstances, Polish heritage or historic building stock is not particularly numerous, especially when considering heritage or historic sites currently used in the real estate market context (i.e. as office or residential buildings). For example, out of ca. 5298.1 thousand residential buildings built before 2011, only ca. 1208.6 thousand are pre-1945 sites, which amounts to around 22.8% [30, p. 21]. However, this class of buildings is one of the classes characterized by the worst energy performance, with average EP (kWh/m² per year) at the level of above 350 kWh/m² per year for buildings constructed before 1918 and 300-350 kWh/m² per year [30, p. 21].

European regulations regarding the energy efficiency of buildings (Directive 2012/27/EU) have been implemented in the Polish legal system by the Act of 20 May 2016 on energy efficiency (Journal of Laws of 2016, item 831) [31]. Importantly, in art. 8. par. 2 point 1 the Act excludes from its obligations the objects protected under the provisions of the Act of 23 July 2003 on the protection of monuments and the care of monuments principles. Also, the obligation to prepare an energy performance certificate for a building or part of a building, referred to in the Act of 29 August 2014 on the energy performance of buildings (Journal of Laws of 2018, item 1984 Art. 3. 1, point 4. 1) [32] does not apply to owners of buildings subject to protection under the provisions on the protection of monuments and the care of monuments. National regulations therefore consider the specificity of historic buildings, introducing exclusions in the scope of energy performance of monuments.

In the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan for Poland 2017, attention was drawn to the need to take into account the character and specificity of historic buildings when carrying out thermal modernization. It was stated, for example, that “insulation of the envelope from the outside is the most common and recommendable solution from the point of view of a structure’s physics. However, there are also cases when, for example on account of the historic character of a building, installing thermal insulation on the façade is undesirable. In such cases, in order to improve the thermal parameters of external walls, insulation can be applied from the inside. The advantages of such a solution include the possibility to preserve the original appearance of the façade and improve the energy performance of a single room or dwelling in a building where no comprehensive thermo-modernisation is planned” [33].

Thermal modernization of buildings is currently becoming a necessity. Current trends in global construction are aimed at reducing the energy consumption of buildings. New guidelines for energy consumption and insulation of building partitions are appearing, contained in building regulations: national and European. The expectations of building users are also growing in relation to the comfort of use and the costs of exploitation. Reducing dust emissions and improving the energy efficiency of buildings is one of the goals of the Polish government. This is served, among others, by the Clean Air programme, addressed to natural persons who are owners or co-owners of single-family houses or persons who have permission to start construction, as well as via ERDF and CF funds towards multi-family housing owners, co-ops and operators, as well as towards enterprises and public administration.

However, it should be remembered that historic buildings constitute a specific group of objects, and their thermal modernization cannot proceed in a random way, determined solely by economic considerations. Effectively, the partial or full exemption of historic buildings from energy retrofitting is possible, especially if thermal modernization or installation of other systems and solutions interfering with the historic character of the building would lead to the destruction of their historic values.

The General Conservation Officer of Poland, in line with the Act of 23 July 2003 on heritage protection and conservation (Journal of Laws of 2003, no 162, item 1568) [34] and the Regulation of the Minister of Culture and National Heritage of Poland of 2 August 2018 on conservation work, restoration work, and conservation research related to monuments listed in the register of monuments or on the List of National Heritage Treasures, and construction work, architectural research, and other activities related to such monuments, and archaeological research (Journal of Laws of 2018, item 1609) [35], did recognize the need for modernisation of historic building stock in the country in line with the energy efficiency regulations of the EU in the Annex No. 1 to the letter of the General Conservation Officer of Poland (signature DOZ.070.2.2020.JW) of 28 February 2020, containing “Guidelines of the General Conservation Officer of Poland on the protection of cultural heritage values in the process of improving the energy performance of historic buildings” [36]. These are not only a set of practical tips showing that the improvement of the energy balance can be achieved in various ways - for example by getting rid of moisture from the walls of the building, by carrying out repair and conservation works in a thoughtful way, by inserting composite glass packages without the need to

replace all windows, etc. Effectively, this guideline is used as a catalogue of possible interventions in heritage and historic buildings. The guidelines for the process of improving the energy performance of historic buildings in Poland prioritize the reversibility, the minimisation of impact and negative influence on the structure of the building, and the appropriateness in the historic context of the retrofitting methods and strategies allowed for in a specific site [36, p. 7].

Another important aspect to note is the severe limitation of PV integration in the heritage or historic building stock. According to the letter of General Conservation Officer of Poland from 15th of May 2023 regarding the definition of guidelines to the acceptability of PV installation on heritage sites under protection (signature DOZ-KiNK.6521.27.2020.EZ) [37], the installation of standard PV systems on protected heritage buildings (roofs or facades) is practically forbidden, as in most cases it is considered to be heavily intrusive on the historical values of the building. In case of the areas under the heritage protection (e.g. surroundings of heritage buildings or certain urban zones), as well as the historic buildings, those possibilities are severely limited and allowed only if the installation respects their historic value.

General overview of the technical barriers in the context of the regulations and climatic requirements of the Baltic zone

In historic buildings, thermal renovation mainly involves the use of internal insulation, which is primarily due to the valuable character of the facades (facade ornamentation, or e.g. buildings made of Prussian wall) and the inclusion of architectural forms of monument protection. Therefore, internal insulation is often the only effective way to carry out thermal modernization of external walls. In the case of historic buildings, there is a tendency to use ecological thermal insulation solutions. An important stage in the insulation process is to establish aspects of object protection and to carry out the project in agreement with the conservation authorities, as well as to carry out the construction process under their supervision.

The possibilities of thermal insulation of the external facades in this regulatory context are severely limited [36, pp. 5-7]. The first aspect to consider is the aesthetics of the facades, as in case they are protected, the application of plasters for the exterior walls is often impossible. However, it is necessary to also verify which walls are protected as, in some cases, only the street-facing front facades are protected. Changing the thickness, form or proportions by adding insulating layers would have too significant an impact on the visual, decorative or historical values of the protected walls. It would also affect the depth of the installation of windows, doors, which sometimes cannot be changed for technical or conservation reasons (if these elements are also covered by conservation protection and it is not possible to produce new elements with the protected old style). However, it might be possible for the external insulation methods to be used in a heritage or historic building on the walls from the courtyard or patio side, where the aesthetic aspect might be less of a concern.

Internal insulation and protection of the partition against the thermal bridges is often the only way out in insulating vertical partitions in heritage buildings, provided that the internal walls do not have historically valuable paintings, frescoes, bas-reliefs, cornices, stuccoes, etc. If they are in fact present, in the scope of

thermal modernization of monuments, we are left with only horizontal partitions (ceilings, ceiling roofs) - provided they also do not have a historic character (e.g. a valuable floor or parquet on the floor, or cornices and stuccoes on the ceilings). However, a building having artistic or historic character in all its components might be typically within a classification of unique monumental or artistic value and not available for any intervention (e.g. a historic palace conserving original ornamentations in all its spaces).

The external insulation methods include thin-layer plasters, blocks made of cellular concrete, or EPS boards are used. For insulating walls inside, typical materials include climate boards made of calcium silicate or volcanic perlite boards, thermal insulation plasters, vacuum panel boards, mineral insulation boards. There are also thermal insulation sprays available on the market, which have similar properties to traditional insulation, which do not require significant thicknesses of the insulating layer. This means that they can be used more often behind historic facades, because they do not significantly interfere with the change of its appearance. A very important aspect in the case of building renovation or premises using this type of technology is a minimal increase in the building footprint in the case of using technology outside and a minimal reduction in the usable area in the case of using it inside - spray plasters simply take up little space [38, pp. 12-14].

Internal insulation systems must effectively prevent water accumulation in this area, and the use of insulation with hydrophobic properties, or with a vapor barrier, are not suitable for this type of work, as they prevent quick or complete drying of the partition in the inward direction. Installing an insulator from the inside changes the physical properties of the partition. External walls after installing internal insulation are much colder in winter than without it. This slows down the process of drying the wall towards the outside and, due to the additional diffusion resistance, reduces the drying potential towards the inside. In addition, in the summer period, frequent rainfall causes additional load from the outside, and it is important to note this is the drying period of the wall after the winter period.

Therefore, it is important that the system and thickness of the internal insulation and thickness are selected in such a way as to maintain the largest possible drying potential also in the inward direction. A board with a thickness of 10 cm is enough to achieve the expected effect of rapid heat accumulation. For example, insulating a wall with an insulator with a thickness of 3 cm and a lambda of 0.45 of a full brick wall with a thickness of 32 cm, increases its thermal efficiency of the U coefficient by 112%. A thick insulator is also an additional place that will be taken from the usable space of the room. It is also important what system will be chosen for insulation. Where rooms intended for human occupation are planned, one of the most important issues is living comfort. For such rooms, boards should be used that can regulate humidity in the air (open diffusion), but only those that can redistribute the accumulated condensate (active capillary). Thicker insulation leads to a decrease in temperature between the adhesive mortar and the wall. The risk of frost will be very high if the insulation is thicker than 140 mm.

Insulation from the inside is associated with the phenomenon of water vapor penetrating the structure of the partition and its condensation. As a result of the low ambient temperature, the temperature inside the

partition drops significantly, causing condensation at the junction of the structural layer and thermal insulation. The layer of thermal insulation on the inside of the partition separates the wall structure from the internal environment, which affects the reduction of the thermal capacity of the entire building and introduces the entire structural layer into the freezing zone. The advantage of insulation from the inside is to reduce the amount of energy needed to heat the rooms to the desired temperature and to shorten the heating time. For linear bridges, the thicker the insulation, the worse the cross-section of the temperature distribution, with a simultaneous increase in the risk for local dampness, which is the cause of the formation of fungi and mould.

2.2.2. An overview of the regulations governing the renovation of historic buildings in the climatic conditions of Southern Europe (on the example of Italy)

In Italy, existing buildings, particularly those of historical significance, represent a significant portion of the national building stock, with about 47% consisting of buildings constructed over 70 years ago. Renovating and upgrading these constructions could serve as a valuable tool for Italy to stimulate investments in the real estate market, support technological innovation, enhance the quality of the built heritage and reduce environmental footprint and energy use. This latter aspect is particularly relevant since the energy performance of heritage buildings is often highly energy-consuming, with severe issues related to users' thermal comfort.

The energy theme is addressed by various programs for national energy improvement, such as the National Energy Strategy (ministerial decree 10/11/2017, adopted based on the EU Energy Roadmap 2050, Paris Agreement) [39], the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (Ministerial Decree n434 21/12/2023, adopted based on the European Climate Change Programme) [40], and the Strategy for the Energy Retrofitting of the National Building Stock (25/11/2020, incorporated within the National Recovery and Resilience Plan and, among others, based on the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU and its amendment directive 2018/2002/EU) [41]. All these policies acknowledge the importance of interventions in the existing building sector to improve national energy efficiency. Additionally, the Energy and Climate Plan (in implementation of Regulation 2018/1999/EU) [42] has established new forms of incentives for the energy renovation of the national heritage and laid out guidelines for the submission of projects for the Program for the Energy Requalification of Central Public Administration buildings (PREPAC) [43], drafted by ENEA (National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development), which deal with the heritage of public administrations as it is primarily composed of historic buildings. These guidelines divide the energy rehabilitation interventions on the building envelope into: (a) thermal insulation of opaque surfaces, (b) replacement of transparent closures, and (c) installation of screening or shading systems.

In these documents, building envelope retrofitting is identified as one of the most effective solutions. However, those interventions are complex in historical buildings since they must bring together two traditionally conflicting fields: restoration and energy-efficient renovation. The following analysis of the technical regulations is shifted into these two areas, deconstructing the problem of the energy rehabilitation

of historic buildings with respect to both the need to protect the cultural values of the assets and to improve their energy performance.

From the first perspective, the major regulation is the "Code of Cultural Heritage and Landscape" (Legislative Decree 42/2004, also known as the "Urban Code") [44]. This code establishes the fundamental principles for the enhancement of cultural heritage. Although the text does not delve into the specifics of building energy retrofitting, it asserts that a historic building is characterized by its uniqueness and must be carefully protected and studied on a case-by-case basis before undertaking any renovation process. In this sense, the code represents a high-level standard that must be considered for any process of recovering historic heritage, whether it is related to energy, structures, or safety. This need for protection was inherited from the European Landscape Convention of 2000 [45], which defined the boundaries between sustainability and cultural heritage, previously maintained as strictly and proudly autonomous in the separate worlds of urban planning and ecology.

From another perspective, various regulations govern interventions on the existing built heritage, both from a technical standpoint and in terms of performance calculation. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2002/91/EC and the subsequent directive 2010/31/EU (EPBD Recast) laid out the principles for enhancing the energy performance of buildings. The EPBD Recast required Member States to establish minimum energy performance requirements for buildings, based on cost-optimal levels. National regulations resulting from this include: the update of the standard for the energy performance certificate (APE) (Legislative Decree 42/2020) [46], introduced to improve transparency in building energy performance calculations; the adoption of the Technical Standard for Building Energy Performance Calculation (UNI TS 11300:2014) [47], the national reference standard for calculating the energy performance of buildings; and the introduction of energy audits, initiated in 2015, requiring large and energy-intensive companies to undergo an energy audit every four years. Regional legislation further specifies requirements and calculation methods at the local level. For instance, in Emilia-Romagna, the Resolution of the Regional Council on September 7th, 2015, No. 1275 established regional provisions for the certification of energy performance of buildings [48]. It set up a classification system aligned with the national one and specifies, among other things, the energy requirements for the building components of existing buildings undergoing refurbishment (mainly in terms of thermal transmittance). Exemptions are allowed for historic buildings if in compliance with the cultural heritage code.

In the context of building renovations, the Strategy for the Energy Retrofitting of the National Building Stock [41], which refers to the EU Recommendation 2019/786 [49] on building renovation and echoes Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency [50], defines renovation levels with a focus on energy retrofitting. In Italy, the concept of renovation is defined according to Law no. 90/2013 [51] and the Ministerial Decree of 26/06/2015 [52], distinguishing various types of interventions. A "deep renovation" is defined as work affecting the elements and integrated components constituting the building envelope, with an incidence of more than 25% of the building's total gross dispersing surface. All other energy refurbishment interventions

that impact the building's energy performance but involve less than or equal to 25% of the building's total gross dispersing surface, fall outside this classification. In such cases, the required energy performance requirements apply only to the components affected by the intervention and refer to their respective technical-physical characteristics or efficiency.

In the context of historic buildings, the UNI EN 16883:2017 standard [53] addresses improving energy performance in historic buildings. The standard aims to assess the impact that interventions aimed at reducing energy consumption in the historical heritage have in relation to the conservation of the elements that characterize the buildings. It is a standard designed for buildings designated as cultural assets, but it can also be applied to historic buildings of all types and ages. The contents of EN 16883 present a normative work procedure for assessing and selecting interventions helpful in improving energy performance. This process is based on investigation, analysis, and the study of the construction, as well as the significance of its status as a cultural asset. The procedure described by the standard essentially allows for assessing the impact of any interventions in light of the conservation status that characterizes the defining elements of the building.

To complement this framework, additional regulations must be taken into consideration to integrate the goal of energy efficiency with policies and measures targeting other key objectives, such as safety, structural integrity, and fire prevention in buildings. Regarding structural safety, the regulations that impose preventive measures on structures, also based on the seismic risk of the areas, include the Technical Standards for Construction (Ministerial Decree January 14th 2008) [54]. In this regard, the incentives provided by the Italian government, such as the "Ecobonus" for energy efficiency and the "Sismabonus" for improving the seismic risk class of existing buildings distributed across the national territory, are strategic. Regarding fire safety, the reference regulations include the Fire Prevention Code (DM August 3rd, 2015) [55], which allows for assessing the fire safety of activities on a case-by-case basis with a performance-oriented approach. Fireproof building materials must also comply with the UNI 10351:2021 standard [56], which has been adopted in harmonization with the European standard for construction materials. Additionally, there is the Unified Code on Safety (Legislative Decree 81/08) [57], a primary-level regulation covering the entire discipline of health and safety in the workplace, whose rules must be satisfied during construction.

General overview of the technical barriers in the context of the regulations and climatic requirements of Southern Europe

Regulatory and technical barriers to the energy retrofitting of historic buildings in Southern Europe are partly similar to those previously mentioned for the Northern Europe area.

External insulation or plastering is usually not permitted due to the valuable character of historical facades, whose finishings and identity must be preserved according to cultural heritage regulations. This criterion applies to both street-facing exteriors and those within courtyards and patios, which often also possess historical value. Insulation of roofs is more common, as coverings, often deteriorated by weathering, are often rebuilt during renovation processes. Such interventions improve efficiency without significantly altering the

architectural appearance of the buildings, but benefits are limited only to the zones adjacent to the roof. Doors and windows can rarely be replaced for technical or conservation reasons, especially if these elements are also protected for their historical value. Interventions on these elements often involve improvement rather than replacement, leading to higher costs and less performance improvement but ensuring cultural protection.

Therefore, internal insulation is often the only effective method for the thermal modernization of external walls, and sometimes also in attics when roofs cannot be substituted because they are historically significant. However, internal insulation interventions are prohibited if the internal surfaces of walls, ceilings, and floors have particular aesthetical value (e.g., when they host paintings, frescoes, or other decorative elements).

During the winter season, insulating a building from the inside brings several key benefits, both in terms of energy efficiency and user comfort [58]. This type of intervention enhances the building's energy performance by improving the thermal transmittance of walls. This reduces the building's energy needs and shortens the time needed to heat the rooms to the desired temperature, thereby allowing for better energy flexibility. Additionally, it improves comfort conditions for the occupants.

Nevertheless, internal insulation interventions must be carefully evaluated from a technical standpoint because, if not well-designed, they can lead to adverse side effects, such as condensation, mould formation, and consequent surface deterioration [58]. Indeed, insulating from the inside is often linked to the issue of water vapor penetrating the structure of the partition and subsequently condensing. Due to the low ambient temperature, the temperature within the partition significantly decreases, leading to condensation at the interface between the structural layer and the thermal insulation. The presence of condensation creates moist conditions that can diminish the insulation material's performance over time. Additionally, it poses a risk of mould and fungus growth, which can be dangerous to human health.

Hence, systems for internal insulation must be designed to block water accumulation effectively within this zone. A commonly employed strategy involves placing a vapor barrier on the warmer side of the insulation, which acts as an impermeable layer to block vapor passage. This layer is meant to shield the insulation material from the development of interstitial condensation that could compromise its effectiveness and eventually lead to its deterioration. Sometimes, a vapour retarder is used instead of a complete barrier to maintain the wall's breathability—especially in the summer when heat flows reverse between day and night, particularly in Mediterranean regions. This allows the building envelope to breathe while limiting vapor passage during the most critical times of the year, preventing the partition's rapid or full inward drying that might occur with full barriers. For this reason, in the case of historic buildings, there is a tendency to use ecological thermal insulation solutions, with the goal of using materials as compatible as possible with the existing ones and promoting the transpiration of the construction components.

Another important aspect concerns thermal bridges, which, difficult to manage with only internal insulation interventions properly, can create particularly critical conditions for condensation [59]. In particular, linear

thermal bridges worsen the situation as the internal insulation thickness increases, leading to an adverse temperature distribution that escalates the risk of local dampness, which in turn becomes a breeding ground for the formation of fungi and mould.

In addition, the climatic conditions prevalent in Italy and, by extension, the broader Southern European region necessitate comprehensive assessments that encompass not only the winter season but also the summer period. The significance of the latter is increasingly pronounced considering ongoing climate change trends within this geographical context. A pivotal concern arises from inadequate ventilation mechanisms (encompassing window openings, the permeability of the building envelope, or the deployment of mechanical ventilation systems). In scenarios where the heat accumulated within the building throughout the day is “trapped” by the internal insulation during night hours, the potential benefits derived from the high thermal inertia inherent to traditional Italian architectural constructs could be compromised (these structures are frequently characterized by masonry elements, either of natural or manufactured origin, which possess considerable mass and thermal inertia). In cases devoid of mechanical ventilation, it becomes imperative for the inhabitants of the building to be thoroughly acquainted with strategies aimed at augmenting night natural ventilation. Furthermore, the components constituting the building's envelope must facilitate adequate breathability to circumvent the adverse effects that may ensue from trapped heat, thereby precluding the reliance on continuous cooling systems, which could require elevated energy consumption levels.

Another complexity concerns the fire safety standard. Internal insulation, if placed along escape routes or on surfaces that delimit fire compartments, must meet fire resistance requirements in accordance with local regulations.

These challenges are further compounded by the fact that internal insulation diminishes the net area available for living space within the building. This reduction negatively impacts the space's liveability and the property's commercial value.

Given the wide variety of situations and construction techniques that characterize the historic Italian heritage, any internal insulation process must be evaluated and conducted in agreement with conservation authorities. This involves a careful, case-by-case evaluation as well as conducting the construction process under their supervision to ensure that the unique aspects of each building are respected and preserved.

3. Review of the traditionally used energy retrofitting methods in heritage construction

Improvement of the energy characteristics of buildings is an important aspect of decarbonisation of built environment which, despite some legal exemptions foreseen in both state and proposed EU laws, also applies to historic and heritage buildings. In the following part, we will present the overview of the possible state of the art methods used for energy retrofitting of heritage buildings.

The general concept of NZEB standard, which is the base goal for the increase in energy efficiency of the built environment encompasses a wide range of solutions for new buildings or interventions in the existing ones, with an aim of severely decreasing the primary energy consumption and increasing the use of clean energy at the use phase of the building. NZEB includes both the improvement of the thermal properties of the building itself, which constitutes the most traditional strategy for energy retrofitting, the electrification of heating systems with RES integration, improvements in HVAC systems and energy efficiency of home appliances. The ZEB standard goes beyond that, aiming at least the net zero energy consumption of a given building by further integration of RES, energy storage systems, and the optimisation of energy use via integrated building management systems [60].

FIGURE 3 NZEB STANDARD SCHEME [60]

However, in case of the heritage and historic buildings, some of those strategies in their current SOTA might be limited due to their possible impact on the historical values of those buildings. One of those examples is the RES integration in heritage buildings, as in case the previously described case of installation of PV systems in historic built environment in Poland. These solutions might be considered as significantly changing the structure and perception of heritage buildings, inappropriate in the historic context, and posing some threat to the substance and structure of building. However, further technological developments in the field of RES integration, and especially PV integration, might lead to the acceptance of certain integration strategies in heritage buildings, such as coloured or tile-shaped PVs [61].

In this context, the most conventional energy retrofitting strategies of heritage and historic buildings via the increase in performance of the building partitions still remains the most widely used. Vertical partitions are on average responsible for 25 - 35% of total heat losses. However, in case historical buildings with very thick walls, these losses might be smaller, up to the opposite situations (as in Gothic churches), when the wall is an accumulator of solar energy given back to the interior during autumn and winter months. Large heat losses also occur through roofs, floors, and windows and gravity ventilation, so insulating vertical partitions is not the only way to effectively block heat escape from the building and minimize its heating costs [36, p. 4].

The following chapter will present different strategies and materials for energy efficiency retrofitting which were analysed separately for Northern and Southern Europe, as the climatic, regulatory and technical context of thermal modernization process would differ. Therefore, same technical solutions might be presented from those two different perspectives.

Traditionally accepted methods of thermal modernization

1. Thermo-modernization by repairing walls and plasters

Carrying out the renovation of walls in damaged, long-neglected buildings in itself often allows for a significant improvement in their thermal parameters [36, p. 8].

- The preferred method of action during renovation works is the repair of wall structures and filling in damages and losses of original plasters while maintaining the original technology of their preparation and application. It is recommended to supplement, not completely replace plasters, due to lower costs and greater durability of this method (secondary plasters are always less connected to the wall than the original ones).
- Plaster replacement may only concern areas that have been heavily dampened and salted in the past, not entire facades. In these areas, it is recommended to use a cheap and safe solution - so-called lime-sand sacrificial renders, replaced with the final ones only after effective drying of the object.
- Renders with thermal isolating additives as granulated styrofoam or perlite are also some solutions for thermal modernization of historic buildings. Minimal thickness of such renders is usually around 20 mm.

No.	Material	Heat transfer coefficient λ [W/(mK)]
1.	Cement plaster/render	1,00
2.	Lime-cement plaster/render	0,82
3.	Lime plaster/render	0,70
4.	Gypsum plaster	1,00
5.	Gypsum plaster with sand	1,20
6.	Thermal isolating plaster with cement, lime, perlit	0,071
7.	Thermal isolating plaster with styrofoam granulate	0,060

TABLE 1 THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF PLASTERS AND RENDERS [62], [63], [64]

2. Thermal modernization by insulation [36, p. 8]

For the reasons mentioned earlier, one should consider improving the thermal parameters of the building by:

- Safe (without sealing) insulation of horizontal partitions (ceiling above the basement and ceiling above the highest storey). It is important to note that the thermal insulation of ceilings, vaults, and roofs should not be associated with the introduction of irreversible changes or threats (e.g., microbiological) for their construction, and in the cases of particularly valuable objects, it should not be used at all. It is always necessary to leave the exposed truss, it is also always necessary to take into account the features of the floor, which in historical buildings often played the role of a kind of “heat pump” taken from the ground.
- Repair, (or, in justified cases only, replacement) of window joinery - the recommended method is the modernization of windows by inserting from the inside a second glazing package combined with proper thermal insulation.

3. Thermal modernization by drying the building (after determining all real sources of dampness) [36, p. 9].

A significant improvement in the thermal and humidity conditions of the building is achieved by eliminating dampness. It has a negative impact not only on the aesthetics of facades but above all on the microclimate of interiors, increasing heat losses from the building. Therefore, drying a damp object should be treated as a basic thermal modernization action. In damp objects, complex action is necessary, preceded by the identification of all possible causes of dampness, and then their effective removal.

4. Thermal modernization by optimizing ventilation

Since the thermal modernization of heritage buildings by adding insulation layers or improving the properties of the existing elements might influence the effectiveness of the old ventilation systems. Therefore, the optimization of the ventilation systems could further improve the energy efficiency of the modernised buildings.

When thermal insulation of vertical partitions is allowed by Conservation Officers (e.g. on walls not visible to the public or with little or no openings), it is the most commonly used method of improving the thermal insulation of historic objects. The basic insulation technologies are:

1. ETICS Systems [38, pp. 10-11]

The most popular method of insulating and insulating partitions from the outside is the so called External Thermal Insulation Composite System. The method is based on the creation of an insulating layer on the prepared substrate of the wall together with cooperating layers and auxiliary materials. The system includes:

a. basic components:

- adhesive mortar,
- insulating material,
- mechanical connectors,
- reinforcing layer,
- facade layer,

b. supplementary components:

- materials for finishing details: plinth strips, protective corners, expansion profiles, etc.,
- sealing materials,
- other necessary accessories (e.g., decorative profiles, around windows, etc.).

Each element of the system performs a specific function and all must be compatible with each other. The most commonly used insulating materials are expanded polystyrene EPS boards, extruded polystyrene XPS, mineral wool, and less common spread foam phenolic, PIR or PUR boards. The appropriate stability of the system and attachment to the substrate are provided by the adhesive mortar and mechanical connectors (plugs). Resistance to damage and the substrate under the facade layer is provided by the reinforcing layer (a layer of mortar with embedded mesh, e.g., made of glass fiber), and against atmospheric conditions, it protects and is a decorative element - the facade layer (plaster finish, facade tiles, and decorative profiles).

The ETICS system has many advantages. In addition to the obvious ones such as ease of execution, common use, protection of facades against atmospheric influences (protection against aging), by improving the microclimate of interiors, increasing the thermal stability of the casing and limiting/eliminating thermal bridges (with a correct design and execution), up to reducing the risk of condensation of water vapor inside the partition.

The basic limitation of this method is the need to carry out works under specific atmospheric conditions, due to the use of processes based on water - therefore, guidelines for technological processes should be followed. In historic objects, ETICS can only be used in exceptional cases and with the restoration of the character of plasters. Moreover, in the case of walls with wooden elements, it is necessary to check the course of diffusion phenomena to eliminate the risk of biological corrosion (most often with this type of walls, an insulating material with a low diffusion resistance coefficient should be used). ETICS system can be used on masonry or reinforcement concrete structures and also on timber structures. In this case wind barrier should be added on board (i.e. OSB) which finished the timber structure. In this case grooved polystyrene should be used (as it is on Dryvit system).

2. Dry methods of external insulation [38, pp. 11-12]

An alternative to external wet insulation systems are the external dry systems. The elements of the system are:

- mounting frame (plastic, wooden, steel),
- insulating material (very often mineral wool),
- windproof (vapor-permeable) foil preventing the “blowing” of the insulating material,
- a ventilation gap allowing for the possible removal of water vapor outside the element,
- facade cladding allowing the use of more noble materials such as stone slabs e.g.: sandstone or granite, but also the reconstruction of even elements of masonry cladding.

The use of mechanically mounted frames, between which the insulating material is mounted, makes the renovation works independent of atmospheric conditions, which is the basic advantage of the method - they can be performed even at a negative temperature, with only some weather restrictions (gusty wind, etc.). This method is usually safe to use in historic objects, and the diffusion process does not lead to the risk of interlayer condensation, as the water vapor diffusing through partitions is removed by the ventilation gap outside the insulating element.

3. Dry methods of internal insulation [38, p. 12]

Traditionally, insulating the external walls from the inside was not a popular solution, due to the risk of moisture forming inside the structural partition and the appearance of mould on the wall itself. However, in the recent years there have been several developments searching for a safe solution to this problem (e.g. the ecological mineral board RenoTherm).

If after conducting an analysis of thermo-modernization possibilities all the possibilities of insulation from the outside are rejected (usually when the historical value of the facade is high and the condition of the facade does not require immediate renovation) methods of insulation from the inside are considered. The most common way of insulating from the inside is a dry system similar to the external dry system. However, it is characterized by significant differences.

The internal dry system is most often made in a wooden or metal frame with the use of mineral wool in mats or boards as an insulating material. As mentioned earlier, wool is a vapor-permeable material. Its use on the inside would result in a sharp increase in the risk of interlayer condensation at the interface of the insulating material and the structural one. Therefore, it is necessary to use vapor barrier on the inside under the wall finishing material e.g.: gypsum boards.

The use-case examples of the described solutions are presented in the pictures below.

FIGURE 4. WOODEN FRAME PREPARED FOR INSTALLATION OF INSULATION LAYER. SOURCE: STEELMASTERUSA [65].

FIGURE 5. EXAMPLE OF INSULATION OF HORIZONTAL BARRIERS. SOURCE: ECOLOGICAL BUILDING SYSTEMS [66].

METAL FRAME FOR EXTERNAL DRY INSULATION SYSTEM

METAL FRAME FOR INTERNAL INSULATION SYSTEM DEDICATED TO PUR INSULATION BOARD, COMBINED WITH ALUMINIUM FOIL VAPOUR BARRIER AND CARDBOARD EXTERNAL LAYER

FIGURE 6. EXAMPLES OF DRY INSULATION INSTALLATION METHODS. SOURCE: SISTEMA MASA [67], SOPREMA [68]

3.1. Retrofitting materials and methods suitable for use in Baltic climate

The thermal modernization of contemporary buildings, and in particular historic buildings, is carried out by applying thermal insulation layers (called insulating) mainly to vertical and horizontal partitions and additionally replacing windows, modernizing ventilation systems with heat recovery from ventilation air, changing the energy carrier (e.g. from coal to gas), replacing furnaces. For the execution of insulation of partitions (mainly vertical), the so-called external and internal methods are allowed. Designers and contractors have a wide range of commercial materials with diversified structure and properties. Materials available on the market include [38, p. 9]:

- styrofoam boards,
- mineral wool,
- glass wool
- polyurethane foams,
- lightweight cellular concrete,
- silicate-perlite boards,

- foam glass,
- natural materials of organic origin (wood wool, hemp wool, cellulose wool, straw, hemp fibre boards, cork boards, wood boards, grass wool, mycelium boards, hempcrete, earth bricks, flax fibre, sheep wool, recycled cotton insulation),
- aerogels,
- Sandwich insulating panel / composite
- thermal, warm plasters.

In the case of internal insulation, an important parameter of insulating materials is high vapor permeability, which will provide an appropriate moisture buffer to regulate the climate in the room, a large drying potential to reduce damage caused by freezing, and resistance to mould. From the materials available on the market suitable for use in insulations of historic buildings, the following groups are preferred [69]. According to different function of the building and used technologies also fire protection and acoustic properties of different materials should be taken into consideration.

1. **Internal insulation system with a mineral board**, made of a material with high vapor permeability, well storing moisture and moderate moisture transport. The insulation board is easy to process. The system is non-flammable and provides a high degree of fire protection. The thermal conductivity for this group of products is $\lambda \sim 0.042 \text{ W/mK}$.

Mineral EcoVario (Renovario) boards are produced based on natural raw materials. Thanks to the porous structure, the material obtains excellent thermal insulation properties. This is a solution used for insulating from the inside of the partition, without the need to use vapor barrier foils. The open diffusion board is friendly to the natural environment. The board is a non-flammable material. Basic properties are the heat transfer coefficient λ (declared value) $0.040 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, bulk density $85\text{-}110 \text{ kg/m}^3$, compressive strength $\geq 150 \text{ kPa}$ [70]. Similar properties are declared for Rheno Therm boards, made of mineral raw materials defined as a silicate-lime board (fig. 8) [71] The boards are made using the technology used in the production of AAC products. Boards made using the above technology are dedicated to the following applications:

- In historic buildings and public utility,
- In buildings with decorative facade elements, clinker brick, sandstone, stone, with the structure of “Prussian wall”,
- In buildings used occasionally e.g. sacred objects, churches or even holiday homes due to the low thermal inertia of the boards.

FIGURE 7. EXAMPLE OF MINERAL BOARDS. SOURCE: ECOVARIO [71].

2. **The perlite internal insulation system**, which is an active capillary internal insulation based on natural expanded perlite, with good moisture transport at a high level of humidity and moderate moisture storage. The system is non-flammable and provides a high degree of fire protection.

An example product is a TecTem board from Knauf. The system is based on a non-fibrous, capillary active and diffusion-open insulation board, produced from refined perlite. The main advantages of the product are the regulation of the moisture level which prevents the formation of mould. The system thus permanently reduces energy costs and ensures a comfortable and healthy climate in the room. The system is particularly preferred for insulating from the inside of rooms in renovation works. The basic parameters of the boards are dry density 90–105 kg/m³, compressive strength ≥ 200 kPa, heat transfer coefficient $\lambda = 0.045$ W/mK [72].

FIGURE 8. KNAUF TECTEM INSULATION BOARD. SOURCE: KNAUF [72].

3. **Mineral wool board** obtained from glass (or rock) fibres. This is a material with a coefficient $\lambda \sim 0.030$ W/mK [73]. It is mainly used for insulation of layered walls, ventilated facades, frame structures, including wooden

ceilings, partition walls and attics. The product is also used for internal insulation, especially for the thermal modernization of historic buildings.

FIGURE 9. EXAMPLE OF MINERAL WOOL BOARD. SOURCE: PETRALANA [74]

4. **The PUR internal insulation systems** offer an optimal energy-saving option for internal insulation, as this product has a low thermal conductivity $\lambda \sim 0.031 \text{ W/mK}$. In addition, the diffusion resistance of the board to water vapor diffusion is several times higher than in other capillary active systems, which reduces the risk of water vapor condensation inside the partition walls. PUR-type boards are most often made as layered boards. A use-case example of PUR insulation used as internal layer (filling) in door structures is shown in below.

FIGURE 10. EXAMPLE OF PUR INSULATION BOARD (DOOR INSULATION). SOURCE: OSTROWSKI [75]

5. **PIR foam boards** are a type of thermal insulation boards made of polyisocyanurate foam. It is the successor to PUR foam with increased fire resistance. This type of polyurethane foam is used for the production of self-

supporting sandwich panels, but also ‘ordinary’ insulation boards. The most important difference between PUR and PIR foams is their fire resistance. PUR chemical bonds break down at a temperature of 200 degrees Celsius, while PIR at 300 degrees. This gives a chance to maintain the building structure and evacuate in case of fire. A variant of PIR boards are boards made of resol foam characterized by better thermal insulation properties than PIR foams.

An example product made of PIR foam are UTherm boards dedicated for various partitions (walls, floor, attic) made in the form of laminated layered boards with an average coefficient $\lambda = 0.022 \text{ W/mK}$, mounted directly to partitions or on separate frames [76]. An example of such product is shown in Fig. 13.

FIGURE 11. ROOF LE BOARD BY UTherm. SOURCE: UTherm [76]

An insulation board for internal applications made of resol foam is, for example, a product of Kingspan company. The product shown in the figure 12 is a layered board – resol foam combined with a gypsum board on one side, and a lining of glass fibre on the other. Between the resol foam and the cardboard - gypsum board there is a layer of aluminium foil serving as a vapor barrier [77].

FIGURE 12. KINGSPAN BOARD APPLIED BY GLUING TO THE PARTITION. SOURCE: KINGSPAN [78]

The basic features of PIR foam boards are:

- apparent density - from 30 to 200kg/m³
- heat conduction coefficient lambda from 0.019-0.024 W/m.K
- mechanical strength - bending, compression not less than 210kPa to 230 MPa
- thermal resistance - from -196°C to +250°C,
- safety for health - safe, does not emit harmful substances, does not decompose
- fire resistance - according to PN-EN 13501-1+A1:2010 Euro class E
- sound absorption - absorbs, muffles sounds, vibrations
- possibility of processing - good.

6. **Multilayer boards.** An example of this type of product is a board made of wood wool with a core made of stone wool. Differentiated layers are a product combining the features of one product - non-flammability and the other aesthetic values. The top layers are made of wood wool bound with cement, while the non-flammable core is made of stone wool with a disturbed fibre arrangement. The board is thermal and sound insulating, allows water vapor diffusion. An example of this type of product is the Knauf Tektalan board characterized by following properties [79]:

- Fire classification non-flammable,

- Fire reaction class A2-s1,
- Heat conduction coefficient wood wool WW: 0.09; mineral wool SW: 0.04 (W/mK).

The view of the Knauf Insulation board is shown in Fig. 15.

FIGURE 13. KNAUF TEKTALAN MULTILAYER BOARD. SOURCE: KNAUF [79]

7. **Internal insulation based on clay** is an environmentally friendly alternative to internal insulation systems. This thermal insulation clay (a mixture of clay and fibrous materials) has a thermal conductivity λ dependent on the content of individual components in the product. This is not a product as effective in saving energy as other presented insulation materials. Due to the lower insulation effect and higher resistance to water vapor diffusion, the risk of water vapor condensation inside the wall is reduced.

The use of this type of materials for board products as effective insulation is practically limited to climatic zones where the requirements for obtaining the final heat transfer coefficient for the partition are not too restrictive. According to available literature data, the coefficient λ for a mixture of clay and straw with a density of $\sim 1300 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is approx. $0,53 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$. Only at the density of the board of approx. $300\text{-}400 \text{ kg/m}^3$ can we obtain satisfactory insulation properties of clay boards [80].

3.2. Retrofitting materials and methods suitable for use in Mediterranean climate

Commonly, the process of enhancing historic buildings' energy efficiency involves adding thermal insulation layers primarily to the walls and roofs facing the outdoors. Insulation interventions are complemented by updating (or, when possible, replacing) the windows and the doors, improving the HVAC systems, and transitioning heating systems to electric-based solutions, e.g. by substituting natural gas boilers with heat pumps.

Regarding the insulation of the building's envelope, three primary approaches can be distinguished: external, internal, and cavity wall insulation. Professionals involved in designing and executing renovation projects have a broad selection of insulation materials at their disposal. These materials vary in characteristics and

properties, allowing for a tailored choice based on the specific areas of the building being upgraded and the construction techniques that define them.

Thermal insulation materials are now widely known and available in the Southern European construction market [58]. Traditional thermal insulants fall into three main sub-categories based on the type of raw materials used for their production: natural thermal insulants, those of mineral origin, and synthetic ones.

- **Mineral-based materials:** Insulation materials derived from minerals are among the most common in construction. They are essentially made from rocks and serve as excellent solutions for managing issues like excess moisture and leaks. Their common features include high fire resistance and mould resistance. Examples include expanded granulated glass, cellular glass, glass wool, expanded granulated clay, rock wool panels, expanded perlite, and expanded vermiculite.
- **Synthetic-based materials:** Similar to those of mineral origin, synthetic-based insulations are also widely used. They offer low thermal conductivity and generally more compact thicknesses than mineral insulators, often with lower costs. However, their use is increasingly declining due to concerns over their environmental impact, primarily because they are difficult to recycle and considered less healthy (mainly due to low breathability). Examples include expanded polystyrene (EPS), extruded polystyrene foam (XPS), expanded polyethylene, and polyester fibres.
- **Natural-based materials:** With the growing debate on environmental sustainability, a movement dedicated to green building has emerged, aiming to offer materials that provide adequate insulation while being eco-friendly to some extent. These materials, for instance, includes wood fibre panels, hemp fibre, and cellulose fibre. These materials often have lower vapor resistance and are prone to developing mould and fungi, making them risky for use in internal insulation systems where there's a risk of condensation. Cork insulation panels are also available, usually more expensive but offering good moisture resistance and acoustic insulation properties.

In addition to the three main categories, composite and animal-based insulants are also available, though they are less commonly used. These materials blend the capabilities of various insulants to balance individual materials' strengths and weaknesses. Examples primarily include recycled materials mixed with synthetic, natural, and mineral materials. Animal-based materials also have limited applications in construction and are typically used as supplementary insulation or within cavities. Examples of these include sheep's wool and animal feathers.

In addition to traditional insulation materials, there are also innovative materials that are still scarcely available on the market and rarely used in the energy retrofitting processes of existing buildings. Some examples include thermal storage materials, such as PCMs found in some tiles and drywalls to speed up the thermal storage or discharge capacity [81]. Sustainable materials, such as those utilizing waste from the food industry, like organic oils and water-based foams, are part of this innovative group. Highly reflective materials, which until now have been primarily white materials with a high albedo, are now available in highly reflective but coloured paints [82]. Additionally, thermochromic materials, which absorb energy in the winter and reflect it in the summer, have started to be produced for construction. An example includes liquid application solutions that allow windows to darken when struck by sunlight [83].

For internal insulation, a crucial parameter of insulating materials is high vapor permeability, which ensures an adequate moisture buffer to regulate indoor climate, significant drying potential to mitigate damage from

condensing or, in colder regions, from freezing, and resistance to mould. Additionally, it is essential for insulating materials to possess hygroscopic properties to address mould issues and to maintain integrity without degrading in moist conditions, as well as to have proper hygrometric properties.

Below is a list of materials available on the market that can be suitable for use in the insulation of historic buildings.

Internal insulation

The insulation of interior walls can be accomplished through various methods, including internal thermal coating, frame-panel systems, and counter-wall systems (which may be self-supporting). The choice of materials can vary depending on the technology used.

FIGURE 14. METHODS FOR INSULATING WALLS FROM THE INTERIORS. SOURCE: STIFERITE SPA [84].

Internal thermal insulation composite systems can be implemented using pre-coupled insulating panels, generally gypsum plasterboard paired with an insulating panel glued to the support structure. The pre-coupled boards may already include a vapor retarder or vapor barrier. Because they are glued to the support, these pre-coupled insulating panels have high mechanical resistance. The final thickness achieved ranges from 50 mm to 120 mm, depending on the insulating material used, which can be synthetic, mineral, or natural (e.g., cork). An alternative adherent solution involves breathable and capillary-active panels that avoid the need for a vapor barrier because they autonomously manage interstitial condensation. These are attached to the walls using adhesives and allow for a fully insulating layer that can be plastered over. However, such "adherent" solutions are not easily applicable to historic buildings due to their low reversibility, as they require adhesive and/or mechanical fixation to the walls.

The insulation is applied onto a previously constructed and anchored metal/timber frame in the framing system. This solution is recommended for walls that are not perfectly square or plumb. For an effective solution, installing a continuous vapor barrier directly onto the frame is preferable. The insulating material is fitted between the posts, and the entire system is then covered with gypsum board panels attached to the underlying frame. The final thickness can be considerable, reaching up to 90 mm in double-layer insulation solutions. Variations include different materials for internal insulation (such as rock wool) or different types of finishes (such as gypsum board, fibrous gypsum, wooden panels, or clay panels). Natural materials include

cork, which can be dry-mounted using a wooden frame system and finished with gypsum board or wood (less recommended due to flammability concerns). Although invasiveness and reversibility are reduced, this method still requires anchoring to existing surfaces.

Internal insulation using a counter-wall involves placing an insulating panel against a vertical wall and protecting it with a counter-wall. The counter-wall, which typically has a thickness of about 5-7 cm, can be made from various materials such as large brick tiles, gypsum panels, or aerated concrete blocks. The insulation, whether semi-rigid or in panels, is mechanically fixed or glued in place, and as previously mentioned, it is necessary to include a vapor barrier on the inner side. Considering the thickness of the insulating material and the counter-wall, the final thickness is also significant in this case. Alternatively, for improved envelope insulation and greater reversibility of the intervention, a solution is to insulate with a self-supporting counter-wall that uses a metal framework with a micro air cavity. This strategy ensures breathability and provides a useful cavity to prevent condensation and/or house systems such as electrical installations, but it requires greater thicknesses. The air gap could lead to worsened acoustics, so this aspect must be carefully considered, especially in buildings used for educational spaces, auditoriums, museums, etc.

Among the insulating materials suitable for internal insulation, the following can be mentioned:

1. PIR foam boards

PIR panels are typically designed to meet the thermal insulation requirements of spaces where internal intervention is planned, offering ease of application and effective performance. These composite panels consist of an insulating layer of polyiso (PIR) foam, equipped with suitable coverings, bonded to a gypsum board. Between the insulating layer and the gypsum board, an effective vapor barrier helps to properly manage moisture flow and prevent the risk of interstitial condensation within the insulating layer.

FIGURE 15. PIR PANELS. SOURCE: STIFERITE SPA [85].

This material is commonly used in both southern and northern Europe, showing similar basic features across these regions. Its essential characteristics include:

- apparent density - from 30 to 200kg/m³
- heat conduction coefficient lambda from 0.019-0.024 W/m.K
- mechanical strength - bending, compression not less than 210kPa to 230 MPa
- thermal resistance - from -196°C to +250°C,
- safety for health - safe, does not emit harmful substances, does not decompose
- fire resistance - according to PN-EN 13501-1+A1/A2:2010 Euro class E
- sound absorption - absorbs, muffles sounds, vibrations
- possibility of processing - good.

2. Calcium Silicate Insulation Panels

These are non-combustible, hydrophilic, fibre-free thermal insulation panels for interiors, made from natural raw materials, making them suitable for internal insulation of buildings, even without a vapor barrier. They are produced by mixing non-quartz sand, lime, and cellulose in an autoclave process, resulting in lightweight and durable blocks from which sheets of various sizes and thicknesses are cut. Advantages include high capillary action, vapor permeability and breathability, non-combustibility, ease of processing, lightweight, insulation properties, recyclability, eco-friendly raw materials, and low environmental impact production. They are also healthy as they have almost zero emissions of VOCs, radioactive substances, and carcinogens. A disadvantage in historic buildings is the need for adhesives for wall attachment.

- Fire reaction class of the material: A1
- Apparent density between 85 kg/m³ and 110 kg/m³
- Nominal thermal conductivity: 0.040 W/mK
- Compression resistance: 220 Kpa

FIGURE 16. CALCIUM SILICATE INSULATION PANELS. SOURCE: BACCHI SPA [86].

3. Expanded Cork Internal Thermal Insulation

Expanded cork is highly suitable for both thermal and acoustic insulation systems and internal and cavity wall insulation due to its high breathability and natural composition. Expanded insulation cork board is completely natural, obtained through a thermal expansion process without the addition of glues or chemicals. Indeed, the thermal roasting process melts the resins naturally contained in the bark, which act as a natural adhesive to bind the granules and form the panel. This manufacturing process does not alter the characteristics of cork; rather, it enhances them by allowing the granule to expand, improving its insulation properties and acoustic performance. It can be found in adherent or dry solutions. Adherent solutions may consist of traditional slabs or pre-coupled panels, for example, to drywall.

Technical data of the material include:

- Density: 110 kg/m³
- Thermal conductivity: 0.038-0.042 W/mK
- Water vapor diffusion resistance: $\mu = 20$
- Water absorption: ≤ 0.5 kg/m²
- Compression resistance: ≥ 100 kPa
- Specific heat: 1900 J/kgK

FIGURE 17. AT THE LEFT: EXPANDED CORK BOARDS. AT THE CENTRE, SOLUTION WITH INTERNAL INSULATED COAT IN EXPANDED CORK, REINFORCED PLASTER, AND FINISH WITH HYDRAULIC LIME AND NATURAL PAINTS. AT THE RIGHT, PRE-COUPLED PANEL FOR INTERIOR USE, COMBINING EXPANDED CORK CORKPAN WITH A GYPSUM BOARD. SOURCE: TECNOSUGHERI [87].

Alternatives include mounting systems with cork panels that are already pre-coupled to wooden battens, as shown in the following figure. This solution can also be used for insulating roofs from the interiors.

FIGURE 18. CORK PANELS COUPLED WITH WOODEN BATTENS WITH ONLY MECHANICAL CONNECTION TO THE EXISTING WALL [87].

4. Rock wool panels

This insulation panel is crafted from medium-density rock wool and is occasionally lined on one side with a sheet of aluminium, reinforced with a mineral fibre mesh, which acts as a vapor barrier. The panel's thermal conductivity value, about 0.032-0.36 W/mK, enables it to offer high thermal resistance across a broad spectrum of thicknesses. The open cell structure of the rock wool can improve the sound insulation capabilities of the wall in which it is installed. The aluminium coating on one side serves as an effective vapor barrier. When exposed to open flames, these panels do not produce smoke or drips, contributing to fire prevention by enhancing the fire resistance of the structural element it is part of. Moreover, this material maintains its dimensional and performance stability, unaffected by changes in the ambient humidity levels.

The solution depicted involves the use of mineral wool panels within a frame system inside the walls. However, these panels are also frequently used for internal roofing insulation, particularly for their fire-resistant properties. This is especially relevant for historic roofs, often composed of wood and other flammable materials, where enhancing fire safety is critical.

Reference technical data:

- Short-term water absorption $\leq 1 \text{ kg/m}^2$
- Specific heat capacity: 1,030 J/KgK
- Fire reaction class in accordance with EN 13501: A1
- Thermal conductivity: 0.034 W/(m·K)

- Acoustic attenuation constant: 85 dB/m
- Water vapor diffusion resistance factor: 1

FIGURE 19. ON THE LEFT, ROCK WOOL PANELS. ON THE RIGHT, INTERNAL INSULATION SYSTEM WITH METAL FRAME AND ROCK WOOL PANELS SOURCE: ISOVER [88].

5. Glass wool panels

Glass wool is another traditionally used mineral material. Glass wool is produced by melting a mixture of glass and sand at temperatures ranging from 1300-1500 °C, which is then spun into fibres. A binder is added to increase the cohesion of the obtained fibres. These fibres are then heated to about 200 °C and subjected to calendaring to give them additional mechanical strength and stability. Finally, the glass wool is cut into rolls or panels under high pressure. This material is known for its ability to provide thermal and acoustic insulation, sound absorption and non-combustibility. These properties stem from its fluffy macroscopic structure, which attenuates noises and provides thermal insulation by trapping large amounts of air. Furthermore, glass wool can withstand high temperatures due to its excellent heat resistance. Additionally, the low cost of glass wool makes it a preferred choice over other types of insulation.

In the subsequent figures, an example of counter-wall equipped with thermo-acoustic insulation are depicted. The insulation consists of a double layer of glass wool panels. The first layer is made of uncoated glass wool panels, while the second layer consists of glass wool rolls inserted into the metal framework. The structure is covered with gypsum board panels lined on the non-visible surface with an aluminium sheet. Similar to rock wool, this material can be used for the internal insulation of roofs, while it is not suitable for flooring due to its high compressibility.

Technical data of the material include:

- Fire reaction class: A2

- Thermal conductivity: 0.031 W/(m·K)
- Vapor diffusion resistance (μ): 1
- Specific heat: 1,030 J/Kg·K

FIGURE 20. ON THE LEFT, GLASS WOOL PANELS. ON THE RIGHT, COUNTER-WALL INTERNAL INSULATION SYSTEM WITH METAL FRAME AND GLASS WOOL PANELS SOURCE: ISOVER [89].

6. Clay-based panels

This type of material is used in dry construction as a clay panel that is applied to walls and then plastered with clay-based products. It serves as a cavity for acoustic insulation in both walls and floors and as a support panel for clay plastering, enhancing thermal inertia in roofs. It can be applied using the classic drywall installation techniques, bringing all the benefits of clay. These panels are usually natural and recyclable and made entirely of clay. They are hygroscopic and antistatic, contributing to the healthiness of indoor environments and fire-resistant.

Reference technical data are:

- Specific heat: 1100 J/kgK
- Thermal conductivity: $\lambda = 0.35$ W/mK
- Water vapor absorption: WS2 ≥ 10 g/m² after 1 hour / WS2 ≥ 30 g/m² after 6 hours / WS2 ≥ 47 g/m² after 12 hours
- Vapor diffusion resistance factor: $\mu = 5 - 10$
- Fire reaction class: A1, non-combustible

FIGURE 21. CLAY-BASED PANELS. ON THE LEFT, NATURAL CLAY PANEL REINFORCED WITH A JUTE FIBRE MESH FOR ADDED STRENGTH. ON THE RIGHT, CLAY-BASED PANELS. SOURCE: LEHMPLATTE [90], NATURALIA-BAU [91]

7. Cement-wood panels

Made from high-density Portland cement-wood (1350 Kg/m^3) and fibres from debarked Pine wood, it offers an excellent solution for projects aiming to achieve high levels of thermal phase shift. Due to its high density, it is suitable for self-supporting dry screeds, radiant floors, and stiffening structures. Its incompressibility makes it a good choice for floor installations. The panel structure is made of wood chips and fragments uniformly mixed with cement. The edge surfaces are smooth, with a grey colour when the product is not sanded. Cement-wood has numerous advantages, including high compression resistance, resistance to climatic changes and frost, good behaviour to insects and fungi attacks or damage, non-combustible (A2 class), can be worked with woodworking tools, high load capacity. It possesses thermal insulating properties, although not as high as those of other mentioned insulants.

Example reference data include:

- Density: 1350 kg/m^3
- Fire reaction: A2
- Thermal conductivity coefficient λ : $0.26 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$
- Specific heat: 1880
- Vapor diffusion resistance: μ 22.6
- Distributed load resistance kPa: 9000

FIGURE 22. CEMENT-WOOD PANELS. ON THE LEFT, PANELS FEATURE A MALE-FEMALE INTERLOCKING SYSTEM FOR QUICK ASSEMBLY. IN THE MIDDLE, THERE'S A PANEL WITH TRADITIONAL INSTALLATION. ON THE RIGHT, AN EXAMPLE OF A COUNTER-WALL ON AN INTERNAL WALL IS SHOWN. SOURCE: BETONWOOD [92].

8. XPS boards

Another solution for flooring is XPS, a synthetic material, known for its hydrophobic properties (useful for sub-grade flooring) and compressibility/walkability. It is extruded polystyrene foam that does not contain CFCs, HCFCs, or HFCs as blowing agents. For many applications, compressive strength is the key criterion in selecting the insulation material. In building applications, this choice is also influenced by the insulation material's ability to bend without breaking in case of surface irregularities or uneven foundation ground, offering low water absorption and excellent thermal insulation. However, it is not a good material in terms of fire resistance.

- Thermal conductivity: 0.032-0.038 W/mK
- Compressive strength: 200-300 kPa
- Fire reaction: Class E
- Specific heat: 1450 J/kgK
- Vapor diffusion resistance: μ 50-200 (depending on thickness)

FIGURE 23. XPS PANELS. SOURCE: STYRODUR [93].

9. Glass foam boards

For flooring, another material sometimes used, slightly more expensive than XPS, is cellular glass. Glass foam insulation is a type of product made from high-quality recycled glass and natural raw materials such as sand, dolomite, and lime. It is an inorganic insulating material composed of millions of hermetically sealed glass cells.

This closed-cell structure traps the developing gas within the cells, giving the material its insulating property and ensuring stable thermal conductivity for decades. No water molecule can penetrate the glass cells, making condensation impossible. The result is a vapor-impermeable, non-combustible material with exceptional compressive strength. Cellular glass in slabs, with its closed cells, provides an impenetrable barrier against the passage of water, steam, and gases. Due to these qualities, and its high compressive strength, it is used in construction as insulation or a waterproofing system for flat roofs, terraces, below-grade walls, or as a thermal break under masonry and sills.

Data includes:

- Apparent density: 130 kg/m³
- Compressive strength: 600 kPa
- Thermal conductivity: 0.052 W/mK
- Specific heat: 900 J/kgK
- Vapor diffusion resistance: Infinite
- Fire reaction: Class A1

FIGURE 24. EXAMPLE OF GLASS FOAM BOARD [94].

Cavity insulation

In some cases, alternative solutions include blowing insulating materials such as cellulose flakes, sawdust, wool or polyurethane foams into the cavities of walls. However, these only apply to construction techniques of façades with a "cavity wall" type, which creates an air gap of variable thickness, typical of historic buildings constructed in the second half of the 20th century (above all in Italy). For an energy improvement intervention, taking advantage of the existing air gap by injecting insulating material inside through the blowing method is possible. The masonry must not have missing parts and/or holes. The blowing system involves creating holes (either inside or outside, depending on the constraints on the building being worked on), about 30-40 cm from the upper floor and about 100 cm apart from each other.

In many cases, insulating the existing cavity alone is insufficient to achieve high energy performance that complies with current regulations. The reasons can vary, such as the low thickness of the cavity, the insulating material not being sufficiently effective, or the type of material characterizing the infill structure. It is possible to combine cavity insulation with an internal or external insulation system to achieve better results, depending on the constraints of the specific building.

10. Cellulose flakes for blowing insulation

Cellulose flakes for blowing insulation is a technique used to fill the cavities within walls, specifically the hollow casing walls typical of buildings constructed from the 1950s onwards. When there are cavities, the empty spaces between the external and internal walls can be filled with cellulose, with the benefits increasing with the size of the space between the walls.

Reference technical properties of this material [95] include:

- Thermal conductivity: 0.039 W/mK
- Fire reaction class: B2
- Moisture absorption: Weight/Volume: <15%
- Vapor diffusion resistance: $\mu = 3$
- Specific heat capacity: 2.11 kJ / kg K

FIGURE 25. CELLULOSE FLAKES FOR BLOWING INSULATION [96].

11. Polyurethane foams for blowing

Expanded polyurethane foam is a closed-cell insulating material used for thermal insulation of buildings and structures. This type of foam is produced through a chemical reaction between two main components: a polyol and an isocyanate. These components are mixed together through expansion spraying, which involves using a special machine that sprays the mixture directly onto the surface to be insulated. The mixture reacts quickly, forming a closed-cell foam that adheres firmly to the surface and expands, filling the empty spaces. Typically, expanded polyurethane foam is used for insulating walls, ceilings, and roofs, but it can also be used to insulate pipes, ducts, and other structural components.

FIGURE 26 EXAMPLE OF POLYURETHANE FOAMS FOR BLOWING [97].

External insulation

In the rare cases where interventions for external facade insulation are permitted, these are based on using low-thickness and highly-performing materials so as not to excessively alter the architectural features and appearance of the facades. Examples of solutions for existing buildings emerged in recent years for such purposes include the following.

12. Thermal plasters

Thermal plasters are the ideal compromise for insulation with low thickness, especially when coupled with another primary insulating material. They allow for resolving thermal bridges and are breathable and fireproof. They are particularly suitable for energy retrofitting and restoring historic buildings, where it may be impossible to install external thermal insulation. Thermal plaster is a special plaster with an insulating function consisting of a mix of cement or lime plus an insulating component (such as expanded polystyrene, expanded glass, cork, pumice, or aerogel granules) [98]. Thermal plasters have thermal conductivity between 0.09 and 0.02 W/mK, vapor permeability similar to traditional cementitious plaster ($\mu=6-13$), density equal to about 400 kg/m³, and fireproof (fire resistance class A1 or A2). Thermal plaster is applied, by hand or machine, on external or internal walls, with a thickness of 3/8 cm. Its insulating power is excellent when

combined with other types of insulation, such as blowing. Thermal plaster works in conjunction with the primary insulation and allows for resolving problems caused by thermal bridges, thus forming a complete insulation system. Disadvantages include high costs and deterioration due to exposure to weathering, which could lead to a decline in the material's thermal performance.

13. Aerogels

Aerogels have been utilized in space technology and are now applied as high-performance insulation material for more effective thermal insulation in construction [99]. This mixture possesses excellent insulating and physical properties, surpassing those of conventional materials such as polystyrene or mineral wool. Essentially, a single sheet of aerogel, with a thickness equal to half of a polystyrene sheet, can achieve the same level of insulation. This would be a significant advantage for many construction projects, especially when thermal insulation is required for existing buildings. However, the high costs of the material currently limit its usage to niche applications, primarily employed in addressing thermal bridges, where it ensures good performance with minimal thickness and surface coverage.

An example of an aerogel panel consists of a nanotechnological mineral insulator coupled with a breathable membrane made of polypropylene reinforced with glass fibres. This panel is designed for thermal insulation in both indoor and outdoor building structures. It is especially effective for insulating internal surfaces, floors, balcony overhangs, window reveals, and any wall surfaces prone to thermal bridging. With a thermal conductivity of 0.015 W/mK, it offers exceptional insulation performance.

FIGURE 27. EXAMPLE OF AEROGEL-BASED PANEL. SOURCE: AEROPAN [100].

4. Conclusion

Deliverable D2.3 provided an overview of the traditional EE retrofitting strategies and the main factors limiting the use of those strategies in the heritage context. In particular, the report identified:

- The impact of climate on the EE retrofitting strategies;
- The main legal barriers to the use of EE retrofitting strategies in heritage buildings;
- The main traditionally used methods and strategies corresponding to the Herit4Ages solutions for future reference and comparison.

Given the typologies of the buildings represented by the demo sites, the solutions proposed by the Herit4Ages project have the potential to further develop solutions for retrofitting strategies which enable their implementation from the EE standpoint, but are impossible or limited to apply due to the previously described factors.

Analysing the material and technological possibilities of carrying out thermal modernization works in historic buildings, it should be noted that conservation requirements in most cases prevent the use of solutions that are based purely on optimization of technical requirements to achieve current energy performance standards. Depending on the local conservation requirements, the adopted technologies may rarely include thermal modernization of the external wall surfaces of restored buildings, but more often allow for carrying out thermal modernization works on internal surfaces. In most of the heritage building cases, it is highly unlikely that the addition of an external layers of insulation and cladding would be allowed for, with the reversible or non-intrusive thermal modernisation methods preferred.

The development of easily reversible installation systems for sustainable insulation boards used in thermal modernization of vertical partitions would therefore be a welcome addition to the market, as most of the identified materials for energy efficiency are associated with at least some degree of intrusion on the wall structure. An interesting solution, worth noting and considering in the context of the project is the use of self-standing frames, constituting a mechanical structure, enabling the assembly of an insulation layer in the form of panels or insulation membranes. The assembly of such frames, using existing structural, horizontal partitions (ceilings), allows minimal interference with the building and easy disassembly, in case of changing the concept of interior arrangement or the need to reverse the object to its original state. We consider such a solution to be worth considering in the case of objects covered by the project.

Nevertheless, this solution would bear the same risks of wall surface deterioration, just as with other internal insulation solutions. Therefore, the monitoring of the environment of the building, using either standalone environmental sensors or as sensors embedded in the insulation panels, would benefit an internal insulation strategy. At the same time, the integration of advanced energy and building management solutions, as well RES integration, while increasingly popular in non-historic buildings, still needs to be widely adopted as a retrofitting strategy for heritage buildings. Nonetheless, given the limitations placed on the RES integration

in some countries for PV in particular, the aspect of more efficient electricity self-generation would be a significant factor for lowering the energy demands of the building to the electrical grid.

Considering this, non-intrusive solutions that do not require significant installation interventions on the building fabric would be preferred due to both conservation and cost considerations. Therefore, the development of the environmental sensors and smart energy management devices (smart energy router coupled with NILM) acting as a plug-and-play non-intrusive solution, connected with a comprehensive platform with analytical tools, could allow the development of advanced building operation, predictive maintenance and facility management in buildings, where it was previously not possible or cost-prohibitive.

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